

**Taxonomy structure of *Agapanthia villosoviridescens* (DeGeer, 1775)
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)**

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Abstract: *Agapanthia (Epopetes) helianthi* Plavilstshikovi, 1935, *A. (E.) subnigra* Pic, 1890, *A. (E.) gazanchidisi* Lazarev, 2021 and *A. (E.) markusi* Rapuzzi, Sama & Kotán, 2013 are downgraded to subspecies rank. A new synonym is proposed: *A. subnigra* Pic, 1890 = *A. villosoviridescens* var. *subchalybaea* Reitter, 1898, **syn. n.** Four new subspecies are described: *A. (E.) v. murzini* **ssp. n.** (northern Armenia), *A. (E.) v. syunica* **ssp. n.** (Syunik area in Armenia and neighbor Azerbaijan lands), *A. (E.) v. giresunica* **ssp. n.** (Giresun prov. in Turkey) and *A. (E.) v. shankhizai* **ssp. n.** (Denizli prov. in Turkey). A subspecies key is proposed.

Introduction

Agapanthia (Epopetes) villosoviridescens (DeGeer, 1775) is one of the most common species in Eurasia with very big area. But great individual variability made extremely difficult the adequate separation of geographic forms. Here a subspecies structure of the taxon is proposed, and several similar species are downgraded to subspecies rank.

Materials and methods

Material was collected manually. Specimens used in morphological studies were killed by ethyl acetate. All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

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Acronyms of collections:

AG - collection of A.I. Gubin (Donetsk)

AS - collection of A.V. Shamaev (Moscow)

ES - collection of E.V. Shankhiza (Moscow)

MD - collection of M.L. Danilevsky (Moscow)

ML - collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow)

MNHN - collection of Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle (Paris)

SM - collection of S.V. Murzin (Moscow)

VG - collection of V.Yu. Gazanchidis (Moscow)

VU - collection of V.E. Ustinov (Moscow)

SMNH - collection of Swedish Museum of Natural History (Stockholm)

SZM - collection of Siberian Zoological Museum (Novosibirsk)

ZMM - collection of Zoological Museum of Moscow University

Results

Agapanthia (Epoptes) villosoviridescens (DeGeer, 1775)

I accept the species with 11 subspecies:

1. *A. (E.) v. villosoviridescens* (Degeer, 1775)

Type locality. Not indicated in the original description; conditionally accepted as Western Europe.

2. *A. (E.) v. helianthi* Plavilstshikovi, 1935, stat. n.

Type locality. Russia, Krasnodar Region, Labinsk (according to lectotype designation by Danilevsky, 2009: “Labinskaya”).

3. *A. (E.) v. subnigra* Pic, 1890, stat. n.

Type locality. High mountains of Georgia, according to the holotype habitus and available material.

4. *A. (E.) v. syunika* ssp. n.

Type locality. Armenia, Syunik province, Goris environs, Svarants, 1880 m, 39°21'21''N, 46°12'27''E.

5. *A. (E.) v. murzini* ssp. n.

Type locality. Armenia, Gegharkunik province, Ayagut, 40°40'30.7251"N, 45°12'15.1285"E, 1420 m.

6. *A. (E.) v. lederi* Ganglbauer, 1884

Type locality. Azerbaijan, Talysh.

7. *A. (E.) v. hodeki* Danilevsky, 2018

Type locality. Northern Iran, Gilan province, Rostamabad environs (36°55'N, 49°23'E).

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8. A. (E.) v. giresunica ssp. n.

Type locality. Turkey, Giresun province, Kumbet pass, 40°32'41.4294"N, 38°26'2.0124"E, 1700 m.

9. A. (E.) v. shankhizai ssp. n.

Type locality. Turkey, Denizli province, eastern edge of Denizli.

10. A. (E.) v. gazanchidisi Lazarev, 2021, stat. n.

Type locality. Eastern Greece, Dasochori environs, 40°53'48.67"N, 24°48'26.12"E.

11. A. (E.) v. markusi Rapuzzi, Sama & Kotán, 2013, stat. n.

Type locality. Greece, Epirus, Ioannina, 7 km SW Metsovo, 1360 m.

Agapanthia (Epoptes) villosoviridescens (DeGeer, 1775)

Figs 1-27, Maps 1-4

Cerambyx villosa-viridescens DeGeer, 1775: 76 (no location, but apparently from Western Europe).

Type location. Not indicated in the original description; conditionally accepted as Western Europe.

Description. The species is characterized by usually totally black antennae without setae tufts; basal parts of antennal joints with fine pale pubescence, which can form white color; elytral setae patches more or less distinct, sometimes nearly totally obliterated, or just contrary very dense and contrast, totally hiding elytral surface; grey humeral stripe present or absent; elytral surface black, often with metallic luster; body length in males: 10.2-18.0 mm, body length in females: 11.0-21.5 mm.

Distribution. The northern most species of the genus, which was published for Karelia (Plavilstshikov, 1968) and Komi (Tatarinova et al., 2007 - Ukhta); eastwards it penetrates to Khakassia; southwards the species is distributed all over Caucasus with Transcaucasia and penetrates to Turkey; westwards the subspecies is distributed all over Europe including Iberian Peninsula.

Biology. The most common species of the genus; larvae develop in the stems of various herbaceous plants; were indicated: *Carduus*, *Cirsium*, *Urtica*, *Heracleum*, *Inula*, *Anthriscus*, *Angelica*, *Chaerophyllum*, *Peucedanum*, *Solidago*, *Rudbeckia*, *Eupatorium*, *Artemisia*, *Aster*, *Aconite*, *Senecio*, *Helleborus*, *Salvia*, *Gentiana*,

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Adenophora, *Foeniculum*, *Lupinus*, *Veratrum* etc.; adults are active from May to July, although there are specimens dated September in the collections.

Agapanthia (Epoptes) villosoviridescens villosoviridescens (DeGeer, 1775)

Figs 1-4

- Cerambyx villosa-viridescens* DeGeer, 1775: 76 (no location, but apparently from Western Europe).
- Cerambyx virens* Voet, 1781: 22, pl. XX, fig. 98, unavailable name - "Europa".
- Cerambyx viridescens* Gmelin, 1790: 1864 - "Europa".
- Cerambyx lineatocollis* Donovan, 1797: 71 - "Isle of Ely, Cambridgeshire".
- Saperda latreille* Fischer von Waldheim, 1806: 17 - "Moscou".
- Saperda angusticollis* Gyllenhal, 1817: 189 - "Europa"; Goureau, 1868: cxiii.
- Agapanthia acutipennis* Mulsant, 1863: 357 - France, "les environs de Béziers".
- Agapanthia lineatocollis*, Mulsant, 1863: 358, part. - "n'est pas rare dans les environs de Lyon"; Gemminger & Harold, 1873: 3177 - "German. mer., Gallia"; Seidlitz, 1891: 850 (= *angusticollis* Gyll.) - "In Eur. bis Schwed. u. Finnland."; Ganglbauer, 1884: 542 (= *angusticollis* Gyll.) - "Nord- und Mitteleuropa, Caucasus"; Dyukin, 1912: 282 - Penza Region.
- Agapanthia angusticollis*, Mulsant, 1863: 360, part.; Obert, 1874: 136 - St. Petersburg.
- Agapanthia pyrenaica* Brisout de Barneville, 1863: 117 - France, "Canigou".
- Agapanthia nicaeensis* Chevrolat, 1881: xcvi - Gallia mer. (Nice).
- Agapanthia irrorata* var. *nicaeensis*, Ganglbauer, 1884: 539 - "Nizza".
- Saperda angustipennis*, Sonthonnax, 1889: 62 (misspelling) - "Grande-Chartreuse".
- Agapanthia villosoviridescens*, Reitter, 1898: 134 (= *lineatocollis* Don.) - "Nord- und Mitteleuropa, Kaukasus"; 1913: 66; Mosolov, 1902: 20 - Russia, Podolsk uезд; Sakharov, 1903: 66 - Russia, Saratov province; Zaitzev, 1906: 121 - Russia, Lykoshino station of the Nikolaev railway [about 58°06'N, 33°43'E]; Lebedev, 1906: 410 - Russia, Kazan province; Pomerantsev, 1908: 498 - Russia, Vologda province, Velsk (Voznesensk-Khoroshevskaya dacha and Priluki), [Now Arkhangelsk Region]; Miller & Zubowsky, 1910: 138 - Moldova, "Bendery"; 1917: 138 - Moldova, "Bendery"; Kiseritzky, 1915: 177 - Ukraine (Poltava); Jakobson, 1924: 239 (= *latreillei* Fischer von Waldheim, 1806); Kiseleva, 1926: 131 - Russia, Tomsk Region, Loskutovo; Winkler, 1929: 1213; Chernyshov, 1930: 12 - Russia, Kaluga province, Bryansk province, Moscow province; Heyrovský, 1931: 83 - Bulgaria ("Witoscha-Gebirge", "Rila-Gebirge", "Kresna-Defile", "Petritsch"); Plavilstshikov, 1932: 194; 1965: 416; Móczár, 1948: 92 - Slovakia, "Jahodná"; Fasulati, 1955: 140 - Ukraine (Uzhok, Uzhhorod, Velyki Bychkiv, Lugi, Pasika, Svidovets); Breuning, 1961: 186, part. (= *lederi* Ganglb.) - "Europe, As. occ. et centr."; Paulus, 1968: 74 (larva); Fuchs & Breuning, 1971: 437 - "Anatolie: Yüksekova (Hakkari)"; Kostin,

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1973: 225 - Northern half of Kazakhstan; Lobanov, 1973: 85 - Russia, Perm Region; Shernin, 1974: 181 - Russia, Kirov Region (Urzhum, Goltsy, Burmakino, Zlobino, Bolvanskaya); Villiers, 1978: 430, 433, part. (including var. *lederi* Ganglb.); Burakowski & Nowakowski, 1981: 214 Poland: "Mazovia", "Warsaw"; Soelen van & Markusse, 1983: 124 - "Netherlands"; Miroschnikov, 1984: 280 (larva); Biström & Väisänen, 1985: 156 - "Finland"; Tsherepanov, 1985: 246, part.; Volkovitsh, 1986: 101 - Russia, Belgorod Region, Forest on Vorskla; Novozhenov, 1987: 44 - Russia, Ilmen Nature Reserve; Bílý & Mehl, 1989: 134 - "Fennoscandia and Denmark", "Soviet Karelia", "The Caucasus and W. Siberia"; Zahaikévitch, 1991: 153 - mountain Crimea; Rabil, 1992: 148 - France, "Forêt de la Grésigne (Tarn)"; Bense, 1995: 400-401 - Western Europe; Carrière, 1996: 562 - France, "Lozère"; 2003: 257, 258 - France, "Pic de la Coquillade"; 2005: 468; 2009: 342 - France, "Monts d'Aubrac (Aveyron, Cantal, Lozère)"; 2012: 49 - France, "lac de Souveyrols (Canton de Nasbinals)"; Lagunov & Novozhenov, 1996: 64 - Russia, Ilmen Nature Reserve; Alexandrovitch et al., 1996: 48 - Belarus; Althoff & Danilevsky, 1997: 41; Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997: 67, part. - Rostov Region, Krasnodar Territory, Karachay-Cherkessia, Kabardino-Balkaria; Sláma, 1998: 351 - Czech Republic, Slovakia; Kovács, 1998: 254 - Hungary; Dorofeev, 1998: 28 - Russia, Tula Region; 2003: 30 - Russia, Tula Region; Landemaine, 1999: 248 - France; Kalyuzhnaya et al., 2000: 193 - Russia (Volgograd, Tumak), Volgograd Region (Kamyshin District, Nature Park Shcherbakovskaya; Ilovlya District, Tryokhostrovskaya); Hasegawa, 2000: 13; Marquet, 2001: 116 - France, "Parc naturel régional de la Brenne (Indre)" Denton, 2002: 268 - England, "Middlesex"; Sheshurak & Sadovnichia, 2002: 242 - Ukraine, Chernigov Region; Inglebert, 2002: 100 - France, Paris, "Champs de mars"; Gouillard, 2003: 128 - France, "Gâtinais"; Sama, 2003: 93, part. - including "Russian Far East and Korean peninsula"; Brustel et al., 2003: 453 - France; Warzee & Drumont, 2004: 49 - "Belgique"; Karpinsky, 2003: 69 - Russia, Vladimir Region; Magdeev, 2003: 206 - Russia, Samara Region; 2007: 174 - Russia, Samara Region, Samarskaya Luka; Isaev et al., 2004: 41 - Russia; Chuvash Republic, Republic of Tatarstan, Ulyanovsk Region, Samara Region; Bolshakov & Dorofeev 2004: 23 - Russia, Tula Region; Negrobov et al., 2005: 601 - Russia, Voronezh Region; Dedyukhin et al., 2005: 311 - Russia, Udmurt Republic; Micas, 2005: 147 - France, "vallon de la Moulière (Alpes-de-Haute-Provence)"; Weitzel, 2005: 72 - Germany, "Mattheiser Wald"; Denux, 2005: 234 - France ("Parc naturel régional du Perche", "Saint-Pierre-la-Bruyère", "Forêt de Bellême", "Nogent-le-Rotrou"); Diego Barquín & Martínez-Porres Cáceres, 2005: 145 - Spain, "Palencia"; Sautière, 2005: 22 - France, "Vernou-sur-Brenne, La Ville-aux-Dames, Noizay (Indre-et-Loire)"; Allemand, Chevin & Withers, 2006: 281 - France, "Commune de Vénérieu (Isère)"; Debreuil, 2006: 32 - "Pyrénées-Orientales"; ACSN, 2007: 107 - France, "Aube: Piney, Rouilly-Sacey"; Migliaccio et al., 2007: 40 - Bulgaria; Simon, 2007: 155 - France,

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“Domaine de Rochebois à Vitrac (Dordogne)”; Ehnström & Holmer, 2007: 26, 51, 61, 278-279 - Sweden, Denmark, Norway, Finland; Tatarinova et al., 2007: 283 - Russia, Komi (Syktyvkar, Shaitanovka, Ukhta); Gorbunov & Olshvang, 2008: 280 - Russia, South of the Urals; Peris-Felipo & al., 2008: 109 - France, “Parque Natural de La Tinença de Benifassà (Castellón)”; Mouthiez & Péru, 2008: 110 - France, Loiret; Kuleshov & Romanenko, 2009: 39 - Russia, Tomsk Region; Ermolaev & Georgi, 2009: 26 - Russia, Izhevsk; Runich, 2009: 58 - Russia, Saransk; Tsurikov, 2009 - Russia, Lipetsk Region; Humala & Polevoi, 2009: 60 - Russia, Republic of Karelia: Cherga river, Chumbozero, Steshevskaya; Krasnobayeva, 2009: 297 - Russia, Samara Region, Zhiguli State Natural Reserve (Bakhilova Polyana, Khmelevoy ravine, Kochkarka, Mt. Strel'naya); Gnjatović & Žikić, 2010: 113 - Serbia (“Niška banja”, “Niš; Novo Selo”, “Zlot”, “Batinac”); Serafim, 2010: 241 - Romania, Bulgaria (Varna); Özdikmen, 2010: 927, 932 - European Turkey; Bukejs, 2011: 18 - Latvia: “Butiški”, Vecstropi “valley of the Daugava”; Týr, 2011 - Czech Republic (“Blatno”, “Jesenice”, “Podbořánky, PR Rybníčky u Podbořánek”, “Žihle”); Antipova, 2011: 74 - Russia, Pskov Region; Bartenev & Terekhova, 2011: 139 - Left-bank Ukraine and Crimea; Danilevsky, 2012: 722 - excluding Korea; Zamoroka et al., 2012: 1167 - Western Podillya, Ukraine (Opillya, Roztocha, Holohory, Voronyaky, Medobory, East Pokuttya, Khotyn Eminence); Georgiev et al., 2013: 113 - Bulgaria, “Belasitsa Mt.”; Lacoste, 2013: 143 - France, “Puy-de-Dôme: Orléat”; Jałoszyński et al., 2014: 679; Švácha & Lawrence, 2014: 127 (morphology); Dobrosavljević & Mihajlović, 2014: 26 - Serbia; Pavićević, Ilić & Đurić, 2015: 85 - Serbia; Kulenko, 2015: 1104 - Russia, Samara Region; Molnar et al., 2016: 49 - Hungary (Fundoklia Valley); Siering & Shumka, 2016: 462 - “Albanien”; Cartier & Cartier, 2016: 232 - “Vienne: Quinçay”; Mazurov, 2017: 217 - Russia, Lipetsk Region, Krasnoye District (Leski, bank of the Don River; Maryinsky forest; Surki tract; Plyushchan; Byk tract, floodplain of the Chernavka stream; Verkhnee Bruslanovo); Sláma, 2017: 65 - “Bohemia, Terezín u Kunžaku”; Haack, 2017: 111 (plants); Haack et al., 2017: 81 (larva); Vitali, 2018: 114 - “Luxembourg”; Žurawlew & Melke, 2018: 86 - “Poland: Pleszew District (Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland)”; Karpiński et al., 2018: 90 - “East Kazakhstan”; Zamoroka, 2018: 684 - “The eastern Carpathian Mountains in Ukraine”; Touroult & al., 2019: 109 - France; Szczepański & Szczepański, 2019: 7 - “Poland: Wzgórza Trzebnickie”; Barševskis & Lecka, 2019: 283 - Latvia; Siering & Beier, 2019: 242 - Bulgaria; Micas & Van Meer, 2020: 140 - “France (Landes): Réserve Naturelle du Courant d’Huchet”; Weigel & Hartmann, 2020: 365 - Germany, Erfurt; Kutushev, 2020: 23 - Russia, Republic of Tatarstan; Aleksanov et al., 2020: 35 - Russia, Kaluga Region, Peremyshl District; Alekseev et al., 2020: 126 - Russia, Kaluga Region: Goritsy (53°34'53"N 35°38'08"E), Yagodnoe (53°32'53"N 35°38'47"E); Dovhaniuk & Zamoroka, 2020: 139 - Ukraine (Ternopol Region): National Park “Kremenetski Hory”; Bacal et al., 2020: 59 - Moldova (“Lozova”;

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- “Bender”, “Bularda”, “Cornești”, “Vatici”, “Ivancea”); Siering & Rothe 2020: 274 - Estonia (“im Lahemaa-Nationalpark in Estland”, “Palmse”); Shin et al., 2021: 4 - “Czech Republic (Bohemia): České Budejovice”; Szafraniec & Łuszczak, 2021: 32 - “Western Beskid Mountains”; Alekseev, 2022: 8 - “Svetlogorsk Forest (Russia: Kaliningradskaya Oblast)”; Saikina et al., 2022: 815 - Russia, Omsk Region.
- Agapanthia* (s. str.) *villosoviridescens*, Pic, 1910: 97, part. (= *lineatocollis* Donovan. = *angusticollis* Gyll. = *lederi* Ganglb. = *acutipennis* Muls. = *pyrenaea* Bris. = *nicaeensis* Chevr. = *subchalybaea* Reitt. = *subacuta* Pic); Aurivillius, 1923: 464 (= *angusticollis* Gyll. = *lineatocollis* Donovan. = *viridescens* Gmelin = *acutipennis* Muls. = *lederi* Gang. = *nicaeensis* Chevr. = *pyrenaea* Bris. = *subacuta* Pic = *subchalybaea* Reitt.) - “Nord- und Mitteleuropa, Kaukasus, Sibirien”, “Turkestan”; Plavilstshikov, 1930b: 32, 40, part. (including var. *lederi* Ganglb.) - “Europa (von Schweden bis Spanien, Italien, Sizilien und dem Balkan), Rußland, Kaukasus, Transkaukasien, West-Sibirien (Petrovavlovsk)”; 1948: 168, part. - North Armenia, Sevan, Arax valley; (Europe, Caucasus, Western Siberia); 1968: 123, 157, part. (including var. *lederi* Ganglb.) - “In the European part of the Union, it is distributed everywhere, starting from Karelia-Vologda-Perm, all Ciscaucasia; in the Central Caucasus and Transcaucasia”, “Western Siberia, northwestern Kazakhstan. In Western Europe, it is distributed everywhere, from Finland and Scandinavia to the islands of the Mediterranean Sea”; Lobanov et al., 1982: 269 - from Europe to the Pacific Ocean, including Japan; Tsherepanov, 1984: 161, 162, 175 (= *daurica* Ganglb.), part. - from Atlantic to Pacific Ocean; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 386, 390, 391, part. (including Transcaucasia); Niisato, 2001: 15 - “continental side of the Palearctic Region”; Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004: 63 - Lugansk and Donetsk Regions; Bartenev, 2004: 41; 2009: 389 - Europe, Western Siberia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Northwestern Kazakhstan, Mongolia; Sheshurak et al., 2006: 268 - Ukraine, Chernigov Region.
- Agapanthia* (s. str.) *villosoviridescens* var. *nicaeensis*, Aurivillius, 1923: 466 - “Nizza”.
- Agapanthia* (s. str.) *villosoviridescens* var. *acutipennis*, Aurivillius, 1923: 466 - “Frankreich”.
- Agapanthia* (s. str.) *villosoviridescens* var. *pyrenaea*, Aurivillius, 1923: 466 - “Pyrenäen”.
- Agapanthia villosoviridescens*, Planet, 1924: 309; Colas, 1928: 179 - “forêt de Saint-Germain”; Perrier, 1964: 116; Sama, 1981: 503 - Italy; Cartier, 2002: 180 - France, “Rueil-Malmaison”.
- Agapanthia villosoviridescens* m. *acutipennis*, Breuning, 1961: 186.
- Agapanthia villosoviridescens* m. *pyrenaea*, Breuning, 1961: 186.
- Agapanthia irrorata* m. *nicaeensis*, Breuning, 1961: 184.
- Agapanthia helianthi*, Fomichev, 1983: 44, part. - Russia, (Republic of Kalmykia, Gorodovikovsk), (Rostov Region, Bolshiye Saly); Kalyuzhnaya et al., 2000: 193 - Russia, Volgograd Region (Tinguta), Kalmykia (Gorodovikovsk).
- Agapanthia dahli* (according to the oral communication by A. Shapovalov),

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- Novozhenov, 1987: 45 - Russia, Ilmen Nature Reserve in the Chelyabinsk Region; Lagunov & Novozhenov, 1996: 64.
- Agapanthia villosovillidens*, Ohbayashi N. et al., 1992: 559 (misspelling).
- Agapanthia lineaticollis*, Matveev, 1998: 87 (misspelling), part. - Russia, Mari El.
- Agapanthia villosoviridescens*, Matveev, 1998: 87 (misspelling), part. - Russia, Mari El, Kirov Region, Chuvashia.
- Agapanthia subchalybaea*, Runich et al., 2000: 85, part. - Russia, Mount Mashuk near Pyatigorsk; Negrobov et al., 2005: 601, part. - Russia, Voronezh Region, Novousmanskyy District.
- Agapanthia villosoviridescens* var. *acutipennis*, Carrière, 2002: 211 - France: "Pic de la Coquillade (Hérault)".
- Agapanthia (Agapanthiella) villosoviridescens*, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004: 126; Egorov, 2005: 17 - Russia, Chuvash Republic; Shapovalov et al., 2006: 107 - Russia, Orenburg Region; Goggi, 2006: 320 - Italy, Valsassina (Lecco, Lombardia); 2007: 85 - Italy, Parco della Grigna Settentrionale (Lecco, Lombardia); Listvyagova et al., 2013: 28 - Russia, Republic of Khakassia, Krasnoyarsk Krai.
- Agapanthia (Epoptes) villosoviridescens*, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 216, part.; Chyubchik, 2010: 117 - Moldova ("Chyncheshty distr., Saerata-Meresheni vill. env.", "Chyncheshty distr., Lozova vill. env., Kodry Reserve"); Özdikmen, 2010: 942 - European Turkey; Sama, Buse et al., 2010: 34, part. - "common in Europe, western Caucasus, Siberia eastward to Ussuri, unknown in Asia Minor and in other countries of Near East"; Zabaluev, 2010: 33 - Russia, "Engels, Saratov Province"; Sama & Rapuzzi, 2011: 142 - Italy (Alto Adige, Abruzzo, Basilicata, Calabria, Campania, Emilia, Friuli, Lazio, Liguria, Lombardia, Marche, Molise, Piemonte, Romagna, Sicilia, Toscana, Trentino, Umbria, Veneto, Venezia Giulia); Drumont & Leduc, 2011: 294, 295 - Belgium; Shapovalov, 2012: 188 - Russia east to Baikal, "Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, probably also northwestern Mongolia"; Shapovalov & Filimonov, 2012: 102 - Russia, Chelyabinsk Region, Chernoborsky; Ilić & Ćurčić, 2013: 89 - "Serbia: Rtanj Mountain"; Ilić, Ćurčić & Stojanović, 2013: 123 - Serbia, "Tekija"; Rapuzzi et al., 2013: 584 - West Palaearctic region; Steiner & Schmid, 2013: 2 - "Griechenland"; Vukajlović & Živanović, 2014: 199 - "Gledić Mountains (Central Serbia)"; Reisdorf & al., 2015: 156 - France, "Marais de Montabé (Essonne)"; Klausnitzer & al., 2016: 558 - "Mitteleuropa"; Facon, 2016: 11 - France, Montreuillois; Dunska A. & Barševskis, 2018: 187 - Latvia; Georgiev et al., 2018: 106 - Bulgaria ("2 km SE of Debelt vill., near Sredetska Riv., 42°22.596'N, 27°16.338'E, 20 m a.s.l.", "2 km SE of Bistrets vill., near Sredetska Riv., 42°18.582'N, 27°02.371'E, 50 m a.s.l.", "1 km NE of Zidarovo vill., near Fakiyska Riv., 42°20.066'N, 27°24.780'E, 30 m a.s.l."); Georgiev et al., 2019: 18 - Bulgaria, "1 km NW of Gabrene vill., 41°22'41.76"N, 22°58'02.76"E, 280 m a.s.l."; Gorshkova et al., 2019: 35 - Russia, Saratov Region; Vlasov, 2019: 105 - Russia, Yaroslavl Region; Stolbov et al., 2019: 209 - Russia, Tyumen Region: "Surgutsky district (Yugansky NR)", "Tobolsky (Ovsyannikova, Penya)", "Yarkovsky

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(Dubrovnoe)", "Nizhnetavdinsky (vicinity of Lake Kuchak)", "Tyumensky (Tyumen, Bogandinsky, Lake Lukashinskoye, Yantyk)", "Yalutorovsky (Lake Singul, Moshkarinsky reserve, Novoatyalovo)", "Isetsky (Bityuki)", "Omutinsky (Dmitrievka) districts"; Gradinarov & Petrova, 2019: 70 - "Bulgaria: Vrachanski Balkan Nature Park"; 2020, 174 - "Bulgaria: Sarnena Sredna Gora Mountains"; Kasatkin, 2020: 234 - Russia, Ryazan Region; Egorov et al., 2020: 86 - Russia, Republic of Mordovia; Danilevsky, 2020: 303 - European Russia, Western and Eastern Siberia, Baltic states, Belarus, Moldova, Ukraine, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Turkey, Western Europe; Lazarev, 2021: 32 (holotype) - Central Europe; Sakalian et al., 2021: 52 - Italy, Monte Sirente; Zamoroka, 2022: 64 - Ukraine; Gubin & Martynov, 2023: 168 - Lugansk Region: "Pridontsovskaya floodplain" Reserve; Donetsk Region: Yampol, Svyatogorsk, Bogorodichnoe, Dronovka, Donetsk botanical garden, regional landscape park "Donetsk kryazh", Velikoanadolsky Forest, "Kamennye mogily" Reserve, Klinkino; Aleksandrowicz et al., 2023: 94 - Belarus.

Agapanthia (Agapanthiella) villosviridescens, Alekseev & Maryutin, 2019: 26 (misspelling) - Russia, Kaluga Region.

Agapanthia lederi, Bacal, 2020: 59 (= *helianthi* Plav.) - Moldova, "Zloți".

Agapanthia villosviridescens subchalybaea, Bacal, 2020: 59 - Moldova, "Ivancea".

Type location. Not indicated in the original description; conditionally accepted as Western Europe.

Description. Fine pale pubescence of basal parts of antennal joints can be very dense totally covering cuticle; basal parts of middle antennal joints very rare reddish; apical setae concentration of 3rd antennal joint usually indistinct; prothorax in males about as long as its basal width, and about as wide anteriorly, as posteriorly; in females prothorax transverse with wide hind part; pronotum with wide and dense central setae stripe; elytra less shining, but without microsculpture, usually with very dense pubescence, which can be grey, yellow or sometimes orange, often totally hiding elytral surface and defining its color; grey humeral elytral stripe absent; erect elytral setae usually long and dense; poorly pubescent dark specimens are also known, especially in Siberian part of its area, where it could be missed with *A. daurica*, but the later has rather big eyes; eyes of *A. (E.) v. villosviridescens* are very small, about as long as genae; erect elytral setae spread back to elytral apices; elytral apices never strongly attenuated, but can be sharpened or rounded; the smallest male among available specimens is 10.2 mm (Kyiv env.) long, the biggest female: 19.0 mm (Troitsk near Orenburg).

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Material. *Agapanthia villosoviridescens* (Figs 1-4): 1 female, holotype of *Cerambyx villosoviridescens* DeGeer, 1775 preserved in SMNH with No: NHRS-JLKB000073628; **Russia: Leningrad Region.** 1 male, Sankt-Petersburg, Gatchina, 31.5.1901 - ZMM; **Moscow Region.** 1 female, Donino, 6.8.1952 - ZMM; 3 males, Podrezkovo, 7.6.1952 - ZMM; 1 female, Podrezkovo, 25.6.1952 - ZMM; 1 male, Podrezkovo, 6.1954 - ZMM; 1 male, Bratovshchina - ZMM; 2 males, Bratovshchina, 22.6.1931, 7.6.1933 - ZMM; 1 male, Mytishchi, 20.7.1933, G. Kostylev - ZMM; 1 male, 4 females, Khrapunovo, 10.6.1993 - MD; 1 male, Chashnikovo, 11.7.1965, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 male, Chashnikovo, 20.6.1972, Krivovyazyuk - MD; 1 male, Chashnikovo, 11.7.1970, Nikiforov - MD; 1 female, Zvenigorod, Nikolina Gora, 11.6.1944, Nikulin - MD; 1 female, Udelnaya, 55°38'22.66''N, 38°03'37.11''E, 585 m, 3.6.2012, M. Danilevskaya - MD; 1 male, Bykovo, 55°38'5''N, 38°4'E, 130 m, 11.6.2012, G. Danilevskaya - MD; 1 female, Bykovo, 55°38'5''N, 38°4'E, 130 m, 16.6.2012, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 male, Bykovo, 55°38'5''N, 38°4'E, 130 m, 25.6.2012, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 female, Dedovsk District, Miitovskaya station, 1.6. 1986, A.V. Shamaev - AS; 1 female, southern suburbs Kaliningrad [Korolev], 9.5.1982, A.V. Shamaev - AS; 1 male, 3 km N Volodarskogo, 30.5.1979, E. Shankhiza - ES; 1 male, Kyiv highway, 1 km from the road ring, 16.5.1984, E. Shankhiza - ES; 1 male, Raduga, 28.6.1997, E. Shankhiza - ES; 1 male, 2 females, Orekhovo-Zuyevesky District, 3 km S Antsiferovo, 7.6.1999, E. Shankhiza - ES; 1 female, Istra District, Manikhino, 27.5.2005, E. Shankhiza - ES; 1 female, Istra Distr., Zenkino, 7.6.2011, M. Danilevskaya - MD; 1 female, Istra Distr., Pavlovskaya Sloboda, 16.6.2005, A. Vdovichenko - ML; 1 female, Istra Distr., Pavlovskaya Sloboda, 16.6.2005, V. Kadnikov - ML; 1 female, Istra Distr., Pavlovskaya Sloboda, 19.6.2005, M. Lazarev - ML; 1 male, Istra Distr., Pavlovskaya Sloboda, 23.6.2005, M. Lazarev - ML; 1 male, 1 female, S of Chekhov, Safonovo, 55.0619°N, 37.4144°E, 12.6.2011 - SM; 1 male, 2 females, S of Chekhov, Safonovo, 55.0619°N, 37.4144°E, 4-5.6.2011 - SM; **Ivanovo Region.** 1 male, Rubskoe Lake, 6.1983, A. Tikhomirov - ML; **Kaluga Region.** 3 males, 1 female, 1 male, Kremenki, 54°54'24.36''N, 37°07'41.92''E, 14.7.1995, V.E Ustinov - ML; 1 female, Kremenki, 09.6.1991,

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26.6.2005, V. Ustinov leg. - VU; 1 male, Vorobi, 27.5.2013, O. Kurysheva - MD; 3 males, 1 female, Vorobi, 55°9'22''N, 36°46'14''E, 17.6.2023, M. Danilevskaya - MD; 2 males, 2.5 km NW Vorobi, 55°9'23''N, 36°46'12''E, 151 m, 17.6.2023, M. Lazarev - ML; 2 males, 2 km NW Vorobi, 55°8'56.30''N, 36°46'34''E, 144 m, 17.6.2023, M. Lazarev - ML; 1 male, Kozelsk, 150 m, 28.6.1993, M. Danilevsky - MD; **Kursk Region.** 2 males, Central Black Earth Nature Reserve, Kazatskoe, 17.6.1990, I. Kostina - MD; **Belgorod Region.** 1 male, Borisovka, 12.6.1975 - MD; **Voronezh Region.** 1 female, Usmansky Bor, 25 km NN Voronezh, 12.6.1988, M. Tsurikov - MD; 1 female, Novokhopersk Distr., Varvarino, 20.6.1988, I. Zykov - ML; **Lipetsk Region.** 1 male, 50 km NE Elets, 3 km N Lamskoe, 26.6.2010, M. Tsurikov - MD; **Ulyanovsk Region.** 3 males, 1 female, Radishchevo Distr., Atmaly Forest, 52°59'N, 48°01'E, 200 m, 14.6.2008, M. Danilevsky - MD; 4 males, 4 females, with the same label - ML; **Samara Region:** 1 male, 5 females, Ziguli Mts., Strel'naya Mt., 53°24'N, 49°42'E, 360 m, 4.6.2008, M. Danilevsky - ML; 2 males, Ziguli Mts., Strel'naya Mt., 53°24'N, 49°42'E, 360 m, 11.6.2008, 16.5.2010, M. Danilevsky - ML; **Saratov Region.** 1 female, Nikolaevskiy Gorodok, 1924 - ZMM; 1 male, Bolshaya Kamenka, 51°48.571'N, 45°42.724'E, 20-22-6-2013, V.E. Ustinov - ML; **Volgograd Region.** 1 male, Olkhovka, 1-3.6.1999, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 male, Mikhaylovka District, Glinishche, 50°06'17''N, 43°31'58''E, 88 m, 17-19.6.2020, I. Melnik - VU; **Rostov Region.** 1 male, steppes near, Rostov-on-Don, 10-25.6.1995 - ML; **Krasnodar Region.** 1 female, Ubinskoe, 9.5.1976, M. Kravtchenko - MD; 1 female, Apsheronsk, 12.6.2010, 300 m, A. Bondarenko - MD; 1 male, Apsheronsk, Otdalennyy, 18.6.1985, A.V. Shamaev - AS; 1 male, 2 females, Besstrashnoe, 44°13'30''N, 41°12'55''E, 800 m, 21.5.2016, M.L. Danilevsky - MD; 1 male, Caucasus, Psebay, 15.5.1911 - ZMM; 2 males, 5 female, Psebay, 44°10'24.35''N, 40°48'E, 860 m, 25.5.2016, M.L. Danilevsky - MD; **Lugansk Region.** 1 male, Voroshilovgrad [Lugansk], 16.6.1951, K. Arnoldi - ML; 3 males, 3 females, Luhansk Nature Reserve (Stanichno-Lugansk Nature Reserve), 10-14.06.2003, V.V. Martynov, T.A. Pisarenko - AG; **Donetsk Region.** 3 males (4.6.2004, 28.5.2010, 5.6.2012), 2 females (1.6.2010, 12.5.2012),

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Donetsk, Donetsk Botanical Garden, A.I. Gubin - AG; 1 male (10.7.2000), 1 female (19.6.2003), Kramatorsk District, Bohorodychne, V.V. Martynov - AG; 1 male, Volnovakha District, Velikoanadolsky forest, 24.7.2000, V.V. Martynov - AG; 1 female, Volodarskoy District, Kamyana Mohyla reserve, 19.6.2004, V.V. Martynov - AG; 2 males, Kramatorsk District, Svyatogorsk, 12.6.2010; 1 female, Bakhmut District, Dronovka, 11.5.2012, V.V. Martynov - AG; 2 males, 1 female, Novoazovsk District, Klinkino, 11.6.2011, V.V. Martynov - AG; 1 female, Limansk District, Yampol, 24.5.2012, V.V. Martynov - AG; **Republic of Crimea.** 1 female, Feodosia District, Kurortnoe, 6.5.2010, V.V. Martynov leg. - AG; **Republic of Mordovia.** 1 male, Svetotekhnika, 18.5.2008, A.B. Ruchin - ML; 1 male, Turgenevo, 19.5.2008, A.B. Ruchin - ML; 1 1 male, Ekaterinovka, 29.5.2008, A.B. Ruchin - ML; 1 female, Chudino, 7.6.2008, A.B. Ruchin - ML; 1 female, Saransk, 24.6.2008, A.B. Ruchin - ML; **Samara Region.** 1 female, Samara, 10.6.2011, D. Magdeev - MD; 4 males, 2 females, Zhiguli, Bostanzhoglo - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Kinel Distr., Krasno-Samarskoe lesnichestvo, 25.6.2011, A. Tilli - MD; 1 female, Polyakov, 31.5.2004, D. Magdeev - MD; 1 male, Sukhaya Samarka, 16.6.2009, D. Magdeev - MD; 1 male, Zhiguli Nature Reserve, Strel'naya Mt., 16.5.2010, M. Danilevsky - ML; 1 male, 2 females, Zhiguli Nature Reserve, Strel'naya Mt., 53°24'N, 49°42'E, 360 m, 4.6.2008, M Danilevsky - ML; **Kirov Region.** 2 males, 1 female, Vyatka - ZMM; **Vologda Region.** 1 male, 1 female, Ustyuzhna, 21-22.6.2011, S. Neporotovsky - MD; **Republic of Tatarstan.** 2 females, 100 km E Kazan, 12.7.2005, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 female, Mamadysh, 55°39.501'N, 51°06.069'E, 20.5.2012, V.E Ustinov - ML; **Orenburg Region.** 1 female, 12 km SW Troitsk, 18-21.5.2012, S.V. Litovkin - MD; 1 female, Orenburg, 3.6.1985, M. Nesterov - MD; **Chelyabinsk Region.** 2 females, B. Miassovo, Ilmen Natural Reserve, 23.6.1985, M. Nesterov - MD; 2 males, 1 female, Tyulyuk, 800 m, Iremel Mt., 30.6.1998, M. Danilevsky - ML; **Novosibirsk Region.** 2 females, Novomikhaylovka, 8-9.7.1987, V. Grachev -MD; **Tomsk Region.** 13 males, 7 females, W Siberia, S Tomsk, Belousovo, 56°18'13''N, 85°11'53''E, 160 m, 2.6.2012, D. Kuleshov - MD; **Kemerovo Region.** 1 male, 9 km S Tchumay, Kozhukh River, 55°39.5'N, 87°49.5'E, 25.6.2019, S. Luzinyan -

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MD; 1 male, Kemerovo env., 6.7.2020, D. Efimov - MD; 1 female, Podyakovo, 1-11. 7.2010, N. Teplova - MD; 1 female, 10 km N Polutornik, 6.7.2009, O. Artemova - MD; 1 female, Kemerovo Region, Mundybash, 4.7.2005, A. Zhuravleva - MD; 2 females, Makarasky, 1-8.7.2007, V. Babushkina - MD; 1 female, Ust-Kabyrza, 1-4.7.2018, D. Sidorov - MD; **Altai Region.** 1 female, Zmeinogorsk, 10.6.1911 - ZMM; 1 male, Zmeinogorsk, 11.6.1984, V. Shilenkov - MD; 1 female, Altai, Kolyvan, Kamenka, 15.6.1984, V. Shilenkov - MD; **Tyumen Region.** 2 males, 1 female, Tobolsk, 19.6.1929, 14.7.1933, 18.7.1933, Teleshov - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Tobolsk, 20.6.1935, 23.6.1935 - ZMM; **Altai Republic.** 1 male, 1 female, Gorno-Altaysk, 1963, Z. Belova - ZMM; 1 male, Shebalino, 26.5.1934 - ZMM; 1 female, Artybash, 21.6.1981, A. Zaytsev - MD; **Republic of Khakassia.** 1 male, Khakassia, Kuznetsky Alatau, 8 km from Balyksa, Terensuk River, 3-4.7.2004, E. Kudryashova - MD; **Kazakhstan:** 1 female, 27 km NE Ust-Kamenogorsk, Tarkhanka, 14.7.1993, A.V. Ivanov - ML; 1 female, Zyryanovsk, 500 m, 12.6.1994, M. Danilevsky - ML; 1 male, 1 female, Zyryanovsk, 500 m, 25.7.1999, D. Obydov - MD; 2 males, 4 females, Putintsevo, 20 km N Zyryanovsk, Maralikha Mt., 49°51'N, 84°25'E, 1000 m, 11-20.6.2005, Danilevsky - MD; 1 male, Sibinka River, 49°36'N, 82°28'E, 500 m, 1.6.2005, M.L. Danilevsky - MD; **Ukraine: Poltava Region.** 1 male, Lokhvitsa District, 19.7.1905, P. Zhikharev - ZMM; 1 female, Yareski, 18.6.1919 - ZMM; **Kharkov Region.** 2 males, Kharkov distr., Merefa, 8.5.1952 - ZMM; 1 male, 2 females, Kharkov distr., Merefa, 13.5.1952 - ZMM; 2 females, Kharkov distr., Merefa, 21.7.1953, 5.6.1952 - ZMM; **Odessa Region.** 1 female, Vilkovo, 31.5.1980, M. Nesterov - MD; 2 males, 2 females, Podolsk District, Aleksandrovka, 15.5.2010, G.V. Popov leg. - AG; **Kyiv Region.** 2 males, Motovilovka, 28-29.5.1912, Vetr.-Zubovskiy - ZMM; 2 males, 1 female, Irpin, 22.6.1980, M. Nesterov - MD; 1 male, Kyiv, Bortnychi, 4.6.1988, V.I. Gusarov - ML; **Ternopol Region.** 1 male, Medobory Nature Reserve, 20.5.2004, V.V. Martynov - AG; **Zakarpattia Region.** 1 male, Rakhov Distr., 4 km SW Kvasy, 7.6.1973, I. Zykov - ML; 1 male, 2 female, Rakhov District, Chernaya Tisa, 29.6.1973, I. Zykov - ML; 1 female, Transcarpathia, Rakhov Distr., Kvasy, 23.7.1973, I. Zykov -MD; 1 male, Uzhhorod District, Nevitskoe,

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7.7.1980, A.G. Koval - ML; 1 male, Chernaya Mt., 31.5.1981, A.G. Koval - ML; 1 male, Velykyi Bereznyi, 18.7.1981, A.G. Koval - ML; **Belarus:** 1 male, Borisov, 10.6.1977, A. Tikhomirov - ML; **Republic of Moldova:** 1 male, Bessarabia, Kostuleny, na Prute, 21.6.1945 - ZMM; 1 male, Meresheny, 6.6.1988, L. Penev - ML; 1 male, Codru Reserve, 8.6.1988, L. Penev - ML; 1 male, 1 female, Kozhushna, 9.5.2009, A. Zubov - ML; **Bulgaria:** 2 males, Lozenska Planina, Mtn., Goliya Rid peak, 42°36'N, 23°25'E, 760 m, 26.6.2006, T. Ljubomirov - ML; **Hungaria:** 1 male, Sátoristye, J. Meschnigg - ZMM; **Serbia:** 1 female, Stara Planina, Babin Zub Mt., 1-7.7.2015, M. Krivosheina - MD; **Austria:** 1 male, Kärnten - ZMM; 1 male, 2 females, Gießhübl bei Wien - ZMM; **Germany:** 1 female, Pfalz, Dahn, 5.1971, R. Schimmel - MD; 1 male, Berlin - MD; **Italy:** 1 female, Forli, 29.6.1982 - MD; 1 male, Stresa, 20.5.1937 - MD; **France:** 1 male, Pyrenees or. Prades, 24-30.6.1986, R. Schimmel - ML.

Distribution. The northern most locality was published for Karelia (Plavilstshikov, 1968) and Komi (Tatarinova et al., 2007 - Ukhta); eastwards the taxon penetrates to Khakassia; southwards the taxon reaches Volgograd and Krasnodar regions, but not penetrates to Transcaucasia; westwards the subspecies is distributed all over Europe including Iberian Peninsula.

Figs 1-4. *A. (E.) villosoviridescens* (DeGeer, 1775) - holotype, female, *Cerambyx villosoviridescens* DeGeer, 1775: 1. dorsal view, 2. lateral view, 3. position of the specimen in the draw, 4. set of labels - photographed by J. Bergsten (© 2021 Naturhistoriska riksmuseet). Made available by the Swedish Museum of Natural History (CC-BY 4.0 license).

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***Agapanthia (Epoptes) villosoviridescens helianthi* Plavilstshikovi,
1935, stat. n.**

Figs 5-6, Map 1

- Agapanthia dahli* Rich. ab. *lederi* Gebl., Bogdanov-Katkov, 1917: 50 - Yekaterinodar.
- Agapanthia simplicicornis* ab. *heyrovskyi* Roubal, 1917: 63 - "for Rossia mer.: Pjatigorsk".
- Agapanthia villosoviridescens* var. *mesmini* Pic, 1927: 7 - "Caucase".
- Agapanthia subchalybaea subchalybaea*, Plavilstshikov, 1929b: 136, part. - "Nord-Kaukasus: Groznyj", "Kuban: Vashtrek", "Fl. Laba", "Anapa", "Central-Kaukasus: Teberda, 7000'", "Majcop", "Vladikavkas", "Lars", "Atshish'cho", "West-Kaukasus: Krasnaja Poljana", "Sotshi", "Abchasia: Gagry, 5000'", "Transkaukasien: Mz'chet", "Borzhom", "Abas-Tuman", "Teliani", "Manglis", "Bacuriani", "Suram", "Kusary", "Kars", "Talysh".
- Agapanthia* (s. str.) *helianthi* Plavilstshikov, 1935: 250 - "Rossia mer.-or.: Novotsherkassk; Matveev Kurgan; Ciscaucasia: prov. Kuban [loc. numerosa: Abinskaja, Korenovskaja, Rodnikovskaja, Mirskaja, Labinskaja, Tul'skaja, Maikop etc.], prov. Terek [loc. numerosa: Naurskaja, Petropavlovskaja, Grozny etc.]; Transcaucasia: Mzchet, ..., Teliani"; 1948: 169, part. - Ciscaucasia, Georgia; 1968: 124, 164 - In the European part of the USSR, it is distributed in the southeast, namely in the Rostov region and further south ... all over the Ciscaucasia; in Transcaucasia found in a number of areas of Georgia; Lobanov et al., 1982: 269; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 386, 391, photo 38, part. - South of the European part of the USSR, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Talysh.
- Agapanthia* (s. str.) *villosoviridescens*, Plavilstshikov, 1948: 168, part. - North Armenia, Sevan, dol. Arax; Europe, Caucasus, western Siberia; Abdurakhmanov, 2012: 32 - Russia, Dagestan, Pervomaysk.
- Agapanthia* (s. str.) *subchalybaea subchalybaea*, Plavilstshikov, 1948: 169 - North Armenia, Sevan, Alagez, Zangezur; (Caucasus).
- Agapanthia helianthi*, Zaitzev, 1954: 19, part. - Georgia, middle Asia; Breuning, 1961: 186. - "Caucase, Transcaucasic"; Plavilstshikov, 1965: 416 - Ciscaucasia; Fomichev, 1983: 44, part. - Russia, (Republic of Kalmykia, Gorodovikovsk), (Rostov Region, Bolshiye Saly); Miroshnikov, 1984: 279 (larva) - Krasnodar; Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997: 67 - Kislovodsk; Japoshvili et al, 2022: 794 - "from Lagodekhi protected areas, Sakartvelo (Georgia)".
- Agapanthia villosoviridescens*, Breuning, 1961: 186, part. (= *lederi* Ganglb.) - "Europe, As. occ. et centr."; Runich et al., 2000: 85, part. - Russia, Mount Mashuk near Pyatigorsk.
- Agapanthia lopatini* Kazjutschits, 1988: 583 - Armenian SSR, Byurakan, southern slope of Mount Aragats.
- Agapanthia lederi*, Danilevsky, 1992: 115 (= *helianthi* Plav.); 1993: 39 (= *lopatini* Kazjutschits); 2010: 45 (= *mesmini* Pic); Althoff & Danilevsky, 1997: 40 (= *helianthi* Plav.); Kalashian, 2017: 44 - "Armenia: Hankavan hydrological

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- State Sanctuary”; Kalashian & Khalatyan, 2018: 312 - “Jermuk hydrological State Sanctuary (Armenia)”.
- Agapanthia (Agapanthiella) lederi*, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004: 127.
- Agapanthia subchalybaea*, Jablokoff-Khnzorian, 1961: 94 - Armenia.
- Agapanthia (Epopetes) lederi*, Danilevsky, 2009a: 657 (designation of lectotype and paralectotypes for *A. helianthi* Plav. - lectotype: Labinskaya, paralectotypes: Rodnikovskaya, Ladoga, Mingrelskaya, Naurskaya, Armavir, Grozny, Mtskheta, Telavi); Danilevsky, 2009b: 715; Danilevsky & Smetana, 2010: 216 (= *helianthi* Plav. = *mesmini* Pic = *lopatini* Kazjutschits) - Azerbaijan, Armenia, Georgia, south of European Russia; Lazarev, 2019: 1340 (lectotype) - “Cauc. bor. occ., prov. Kuban, Labinskaja”.
- Agapanthia (Epopetes) lederi lederi*, Danilevsky, 2020: 302, part. - south of European Russia, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Turkey.

Type locality. Russia, Krasnodar Region, Labinsk [44°38'N, 40°44'E] (according to lectotype designation by Danilevsky, 2009: “Labinskaya”).

Description. Antennae in males surpassing elytral apices by 5 apical joints, in females - by 3-4 joints; basal parts of antennal joints with very fine pale pubescence, and look rather dark; basal parts of middle antennal joints usually reddish; one male from Tsagveri (Georgia) has red antennae; 3rd antennal joint with apical setae concentration; prothorax in males and in females transverse, widened posteriorly; pronotum with wide and dense central setae stripe; elytra shining, but without blue luster, without microsculpture, with usually poor greyish pubescence, which sometimes can be rather dense (Teberda); grey humeral elytral stripe often distinct; erect elytral setae long and dense along anterior elytral third, and gradually shortened posteriorly; elytral apices slightly attenuated; body length in males: 10.5-18.0 mm, female length: 11.0-21.5 mm.

The taxon differs from the nominative subspecies by less pubescent elytra and often presence of grey humeral elytral stripe.

Material. Russia: Krasnodar Region. 2 males, 1 female, Kuban, Bolshaya Laba River - ZMM; 1 male, Ekaterinodar [Krasnodar], 26.4.1911 - ZMM; 1 male, Armavir. 6.6.1912 - ZMM; 3 males, Armavir - Natyrbovo - ZMM; 2 males, Sochi, 18-19.6.1913, Zicharev - ZMM; 1 female, Sochi, 5.1986, A.Yu. Veselova - MD; 1 male, Sochi, 19.6.1913 - ZMM; 1 male, Sochi, Utch-Dere - ZMM; 1 male, 3 females, Sochi, 5.1986, L.Yu. Veselova - ML; 1 female,

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Anapa, 13.7.1911, Zhikharev - ZMM; 2 males, Anapa, 27.6.1911, Zhikharev - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Kuban, Mingrelskoe, 10.5.1930, V. Galkin - ZMM; 1 male, Kuban prov., Ladozhskaya, 6.VI. - ZMM; 4 males, 5 females, Caucasus, Goryachy Klyuch, 5.1938, M. Lutchnik - ZMM; 3 females, Goryachy Klyuch, Shchetka Mt., 21.6.1987, N. Okhrimenko - MD; 1 female, Betta, 44°13'45.4853"N, 39°14'24.7287"E, 27.5.2011, V. Ustinov - VU; **Republic of Adygea.** Lectotype, male (length: 14.3 mm; width: 3.5 mm) with 5 labels: 1) [red] "Type"; 2) "Cauc. bor. occ. / prov. Kuban / Labinskaja / 19.VI.[1]914"; 3) "*Agapanthia / helianthi* / m. / N. Plavilstshikov det."; 4) [red] "LECTOTYPUS / *Agapanthia HELIANTHI* / Plavilstshikov, 1935 / M. Danilevsky des., 2008"; 5) [pink] "Зоомузей МГУ (Москва, РОССИЯ) / № ZMMU Col 00141 / Zool. Mus. Mosq. Univ. / (Mosquae, ROSSIA) / ex coll. N. N. Plavilstshikov" - ZMM; Paralectotype, male with three labels: 1) [red] "Cotype", 2) "Caucas. bor. / distr. Maikop / p. Rodnikovskaya, 1.VI 1930", 3) "*Agapanthia / helianthi* / m / N. Plavilstshikov det." - SZM; 1 male, 3 females, Maikop, Rodnikovskaya, 15.5.1930, B. Dobrovolsky - ZMM; 5 males, Maikop, Rodnikovskaya, 1.6.1930 - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Maikop, 30.5.1929 - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Maikop, 12-13.6.1933 - ZMM; 2 males, Maikop, 1.6.1933, 26.6.1933, Arnoldi - ZMM; 1 male, Maikop, 5.6.1935 -ZMM; 2 males, Maikop, 4.5.1947 - ZMM; 2 females, Maikop, 15.5.1951, 18.5.1952 - ZMM; 1 male, 10 km SW Krasnodar, Khomuty, 21.6.1988, V.I. Gusarov - ML; 4 males, 2 females, Khomuty, 6.1973, A. Miroshnikov - MD; **Karachay-Cherkessia Republic.** 1 female, Kuban, Teberda - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Teberda, A. Zolotarew - ZMM; 1 male, Cauc. sept. Teberda, Popova g., 19.6.1908, A. Zolotarew - ZMM; 36 males, 23 females, Teberda, 2.6.1930, P. Elagin - ZMM; 7 males, 6 females, Teberda, 30.5.1931, P. Elagin - ZMM; 1 male, Teberda, 20.7.1964, A. Tikhomirova - ZMM; 1 female, Teberda, 4200`, S. Tschetweikow - ZMM; 1 male, Cauc. cent, bor. Teberda, 7000`, A. Zolotarew - ZMM; 3 females, Teberda, 24.5.1940, 8.6.1940 - MD; 1 male, Teberda, Mukha, 25.6.1916 - MD; 4 males, 2 females, N Caucasus, Teberda, 1700-1800 m, watershed Dzhenaït and Korylykaya Rivers, 22.6.1993, V. Savitsky - MD; 1 female, Caucasus, Zelenchukskaya, 26.5.1949, M. Stavskaya - ZMM; **Stavropol Region.** 1 male, Cauc.

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bor. Stavropol, 5.1914, B. Zolotarevsky - ZMM; 1 male, Cauc. bor. Stavropol, 7-13.5.1914, B. Zolotarevsky - ZMM; 1 male, Cauc. bor. Stavropol, 1-10.6.1914, B. Zolotarevsky - ZMM; 1 female, Caucas. bor., Stavropol, 13.5.1914, A. Zolotarew - ZMM; 1 male, Kislovodsk - ZMM; 1 male, Kislovodsk, 6.1913, N. Plavilstchikov - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Kislovodsk env, 1-10.6.2003, Y. Liman - ML; 1 female, near Kislovodsk, Beriozovaya River, 1000 m, 10.6.1995 - SM; 1 male, Zheleznovodsk, 9.6.1907, Pliginsky - ZMM; 2 males, Zheleznovodsk, 11.5.1909, J. Parfentiev - ZMM; 1 female, Caucasus, Mineralnye Vody, Mashuk, 13.5.1909, J. Parfentiev - ZMM; 3 males, 1 female, Mashuk, 44°2'51.26"N, 43°6'2"E, 29.4.2024, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 female, Mashuk, 44°2'49"N, 43°4'55"E, 26.4.2024, M. Danilevsky - MD; 3 males, Mashuk, 44°03.020'N, 43°04.186'E, 25.4.2024, V. Ustinov - VU; 5 males, Pyatigorsk, Kolstevaya str., 44°05.301'N, 43°00.694'E, 28.4.2024, V. Ustinov - VU; 2 males, 1 female, Pyatigorsk, Proval env., 29.4.2024, V. Ustinov - VU; 1 male, Temnolesskaya, 31.5.1950, O. Kryzhanovski - ZMM; **Republic of North Ossetia-Alania.** 1 male, Mont. prope Wladikavkas, A Zolotarew - ZMM; 1 male, 2 females, Mozdok, 27.5.1982, V. Janushev - MD; **Republic of Ingushetia.** 1 female, Nizhniy Alkun [Alkun], 8.6.1958, B. Vorobev - ZMM; **Chechen Republic.** 1 female, Grozny, Luchnik - ZMM; 1 female, Grozny, 1909, Luchnik - ZMM; 1 male, Grozny, 20.5.1913, N. Plavilstchikov - ZMM; 2 males, 2 females, Naurskaya, 4.6.1913, N. Plavilstshikov - ZMM; 1 male, Chechnya, Starogladkovskaya, Terek River, 23.6.1928, Arnoldi - MD; **Republic of Dagestan.** 1 female, Kizlyar, 25.6.1932 - ZMM; 2 males, Khasavyurt, 14.6.1953, 18.8.1953 - ZMM; 1 male, 2 females, Novy Biryuzak, 21.5.1959, B. Vorobev - ZMM; **Georgia:** 1 male, Manglisi, 22.VI. - ZMM; 2 males, Manglisi, 1200 m, 16.6.1990, M. Danilivsky - MD, ML; 1 female, Bakuriani, 7.1924 - ZMM; 1 female, Bakuriani, 19.7.1909, J. Parfentiev - ZMM; 3 females, Bakuriani, 11.7.1930, N. Kotova - ZMM; 4 males, 4 females, Bakuriani, 24.7.1930, N. Kotova - ZMM; 1 male, Bakuriani, 29.7.1930, N. Kotova - ZMM; 2 males, Teliani prope, Telav, Kakhetia, 20.06.1907, N.J. Fursov - ZMM; 1 male, Kakheti, 24.8. - ZMM; 1 male, Mtschet, prope Tiflis, 9.6.1915, B. Uvarov - ZMM; 1 male, Mtskheta, 31.5.1914, L. Bankovsky - ZMM; 1 female,

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Mtschet, prope Tiflis, 8.1915 - ZMM; 1 male, Tiflis, Suram, 28.5.1882 - ZMM; 1 male, Surami, 5.6.1917, C. Ahnger - ZMM; 1 male, Tsagveri, 25.5.1967, I. Dzhavelidze - MD; 1 female, Tsagveri, 21.6.1982, V. Dolin - MD; 2 males, Tsagveri, 23.7.1987, M. Danilevsky - ML; 1 female, Borzhom, 6.1925 - ZMM; 1 male, Borzhomi, 18.7.1902 - MD; 1 female, Borzhomi, 2.8.1987, O. Gorbunov - ML; 1 male, Tbilisi, Satovle Ridge, 1300-1400 m, 18.6.1985, S. Kyzmin - MD; 1 female, Mskhmeta, 22.5.1985, R.D. Zhantiev - ML; 8 males, 6 females, Akhaldaba, 15.7.1987, M. Danilevsky - MD; 5 males, 3 females, Akhaldaba, 600 m, 15.7.1987, M. Danilevsky - ML; 1 male, Orbeti, Trialiti Ridge, 28-29.5.2016, A. Zubov - MD; **Armenia:** 1 male, Erivan Distr., Darachichag [Tsaghkadzor], 20.6.1912, Dobrovljanski - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Transcauc., Erivan Distr., Darachichag, 14-17.7.1912, Dobrovljanski - ZMM; 1 male, Darachichag, 6.1935 - ZMM; 1 female, Inaklyu [Antarut], 26.7.1934, B. Tkatchukov - ZMM; 1 female, Alagez [Aragats Mount], Inaklyu, 6.1935 - ZMM; 1 male, Alagez, Inaklyu, 25.7.1936 - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Alagez, Inaklyu, 26.7.1936 - ZMM; 1 female, Alagez, Inaklyu, 28.6.1956, A. Tsvetaev - ZMM; 1 female, Daratchitchag, Maljushenko - ZMM; 4 males, 1 female, Daratchitchag, 14-17.7.1912, Dobrovljansky - ZMM; 1 male, Idzhevan, 26.5.1935, A. Zagulyaev - ZMM; 2 females, Darachichag, 7.1935 - ZMM; 1 female, Idzhevan, 26.5.1955, L. Zomina - ZMM; 1 male, Idzhevan, 26.5.1955, L. Zimina - ZMM; 1 male, Idzhevan, Kirants, 30.4.1989, M. Kalashian - MD; 2 males, Idzhevan, Kirants, 20.4-2.5.1989, M. Kalashian - ML; 1 female, Tavush, Ditavan, 40.955°N, 45.222°E, 1400 m, 27.6.2015, S. Murzin - ML; 1 female, Geghard, 8.6.1989, M. Kalashian - ML; 1 female, Geghard, 40.1414°N, 44.8074°E, 1800 m, 19.5.2013, S. Murzin - SM; 1 female, Khosrov, 7.8.1967, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 female, Khosrov, 1.7.1983, V. Kuznetsov - ML; 1 female, Khosrov, 2.7.1983, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Khosrov, 24.6.1984, V. Kuznetsov - ML; 1 male, 1 female, Khosrov, 25.6.1986, M.Yu. Kalashian - ML; 2 males, 4 females, Khosrov, 25.6.1991, M. Kalashian - MD; 2 males, 1 female, Khosrov, 24.7.1991, M. Kalashian - MD; 2 males, Khosrov, 1-3.6.1992, A. Sukiasian - VU; 1 male, Khosrov, 19.8.2002, M. Kalashian - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Khosrov, 24.6.1992, M. Kalashian - MD; 1 male, 1 male,

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Khosrov, 5.6.1982, Dolin - ML; 1 male, 1 female, Khosrov Reserve, Central aerea, E slope of Kotuts Mt., 9.6.2002, M. Kalashian - SM; 1 male, Khosrov, 40°02'N, 45°02'E, 10-12.6.2003, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 female, Byurakan, 17.6.2003, 1700 m, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 male, 3 females, Arailer, 1900-2000 m, 18-21.6.2003, M. Danilevsky - MD; **Azerbaijan**: 1 female, Transcaucasia, Arax, Sabir-Abad, 8.VI. - ZMM; 2 female, Qusar, 1.7.1900, 10.7.1900, A. Zavadsk - ZMM; 1 male, 1 male, Transcaucasia, Akstafa, 13.6.1907, D. Skorospelov - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Barda, 26.6.1933, F. Lukjanovitch - ZMM; 1 female, Nukha [Shaki], 25.6.1933, F. Lukjanovich - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Nukha, 25.7.1933, F. Lukjanovitch - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Altyagach, 9.7.1979, M. Danilevsky - MD.

Distribution. North Caucasus without very high areas from Krasnodar Region to Daghestan; Transcaucasia: Azerbaijan without Talysh, Armenia without north Trans Sevan mountains and without south Meghri environs, Georgia without high mountains.

Agapanthia (Epopetes) villosoviridescens subnigra Pic, 1890, stat. n.

Figs 7-9, Map 1

- Agapanthia subnigra* Pic, 1890: 119 - "Georgie"; Winkler, 1929: 1213; Danilevsky, 2010: 44; Sama et al., 2008: 122 (?= *subchalybaea* Pic) - "Caucasus", "absent in Iran".
- Agapanthia villosoviridescens* var. *subchalybaea* Reitter, 1898: 134 - "Kaukasus und Turkestan: Taschkend"; Winkler, 1929: 1213 - "Ca. Tk.", **syn. n.**
- Agapanthia angusticollis* v. *subacuta* Pic, 1909: 106 - "Caucase".
- Agapanthia* (s. str.) *villosoviridescens*, Pic, 1910: 97, part. (= *lineotocollis* Donov., = *angusticollis* Gyll., = *lederi* Ganglb., = *acutipennis* Muls., = *pyrenaea* Bris., = *nicaeensis* Chevr., = *subchalybaea* Reitt., = *subacuta* Pic).
- Agapanthia* (s. str.) *subnigra*, Pic, 1910: 97 - "Caucase"; Aurivillius, 1923: 464, part. - "Kaukasus".
- Agapanthia* (s. str.) *villosoviridescens* var. *subchalybaea*, Aurivillius, 1923: 466, part. - "Kaukasus, Turkestan".
- Agapanthia* (s. str.) *villosoviridescens* var. *subacuta*, Aurivillius, 1923: 466, part. - "Kaukasus".
- Agapanthia subchalybaea subchalybaea*, Plavilstshikov, 1929: 103, part. - "Caucasus"; 1930a: 131.
- Agapanthia* (s. str.) *subchalybaea subchalybaea*, Plavilstshikov, 1930b: 34, 40, part. (= *subacuta* Pic = *subnigra* Pic); 1948: 169, part. - North Armenia, Sevan, Alagez, Zangezur; (Caucasus).

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- Agapanthia subchalybaea*, Plavilstshikov, 1932: 194, part. - Caucasus; 1965: 416, part. - Caucasus; Zaitzev, 1954: 19, part. - Georgia: Borjomi, Gvirgvina, Tana, Tsagveri, Akhaldaba, Saguramo, Mtskheta, Tbilisi, Lagodekhi, Armenia, middle Asia; Breuning, 1961: 186, part. (= *subacuta* Pic, = *subnigra* Pic, = *turanica* Plav.) - "Caucase, Transcaucasie"; Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997: 67, part. - Krasnodar Krai: Ust-Labinsk, Nickel; Karachayevo-Cherkessia: Teberda, ridge Arkasara; Kabardino-Balkaria: Dolina Narzanov, 1350 m, 43°41'50"N, 42°40'28"E; Danilevsky, 2010: 44.
- Agapanthia subchalybaea* m. *subnigra*, Breuning, 1961: 186.
- Agapanthia subchalybaea* m. *subacuta*, Breuning, 1961: 186.
- Agapanthia* (s. str.) *subchalybaea*, Plavilstshikov, 1968: 123, 159, part. (= *subacuta* Pic = *subnigra* Pic) - Caucasus with Transcaucasia. Northeastern Turkey; Lobanov et al., 1982: 269; Danilevsky, Mirosnikov, 1985: 386, 391 - Caucasus, Transcaucasia; Northeast Turkey.
- Agapanthia* (*Agapanthiella*) *subnigra*, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004: 127.
- Agapanthia* (*Agapanthiella*) *subchalybaea*, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004: 127; Özdikmen, 2007: 349, 392, part. (?= *subnigra* Pic) - Turkey.
- Agapanthia* (*Epopetes*) *subnigra*, Danilevsky & Smetana, 2010: 216, part. - Azerbaijan, Georgia, Russia: South European Territory; Danilevsky, 2020: 303 - Georgia.
- Agapanthia* (*Epopetes*) *subchalybaea*, Danilevsky & Smetana, 2010: 216 (= *subacuta* Pic), part. - Azerbaijan, Georgia, Russia: South European Territory; Özdikmen, 2013: 20 - Turkey: Konya; Danilevsky, 2020: 303, part. - Azerbaijan, Georgia, Russia: South European Territory.
- ?*Agapanthia subchalybaea*, Şabanoglu, 2020: 204 (misspelling, unavailable name) - Turkey: Rize: İkizdere.

Type locality. High mountains of Georgia, according to the holotype habitus and available material.

Description. Antennae reaching elytral apex by 6th-8th joints in males, in females - by 9th-10th joints; basal parts of antennal joints with very fine pale pubescence, and look rather dark; basal parts of middle antennal joints never reddish; 3rd antennal joint with apical setae concentration; prothorax in males about as long as wide, and about as wide anteriorly, as posteriorly; in females prothorax transverse with wider hind part; pronotum with narrow setae stripe, often more or less reduced; elytra about glabrous, with poor bluish luster, recumbent pubescence often indistinct, but with dense erect setae present up to the apex; microsculpture absent; body length in males: 11.2-16.4 mm, in females: 11.4-18.7 mm.

This high mountain taxon is close to *A. v. helianthi* Plav. but can be easily identified by poor elytral pubescence and bluish luster.

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Material. Russia: Krasnodar Region. 1 male, 2 females, Circassia, Kardyvach, 20.6.1912, I. Michelson - ZMM; 2 males, Atchishkho, 1600 m, 28.6.1973, A. Lobanov - MD; 1 female, Cauc. occ., Krasnaya Polyana, VIII, Dr. Lgocki - ZMM; 3 males, 1 female, Krasnaya Polyana, 26.7.1910 - ZMM; 1 male, Krasnaya Polyana, 1952, Zhelokhovtsev - ZMM; 4 males, 2 females, Cauc., Krasnaya Polyana, 9-15.8.1952, Zhelokhovtsev - ZMM; 2 males, Atchishkho, 800-1500 m, 10.8.2003, 23.6.2005, V. Savitsky - MD; 1 male, Novorossiysk, Andreevsky pass, 500 m, 44°43'N, 37°51'E, 5.6.2010, M. Danilevsky - MD; **Republic of Adygea.** 1 female, Abago Mt., 2100 m, 29-30.6.1999, Puchkov - MD; 1 female, Russia, westwards Tkhach Mt., 1700-1900 m, 20.7.2002, V. Savitsky - MD; 1 male, Lagonaki, Ridge, Kamennoe More, 1760-1800 m, 44°10'33"N, 40°03'19"E, 7-19.6.2012, A.V. Korshunov - MD; **Karachay-Cherkessia Republic.** 1 male, Damkhurts, 29.7.1967, N. Filippov - MD; 1 female, from same locality, 14.8.1967, N. Filippov - MD; 1 female, from same locality, 18.8.1967, S. Sharova - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Bolshaya Laba River, Pkhiya, 1400-1600 m, 29.8.1992, V. & M. Savitsky - MD; 2 males, 2 females, Bolshaya Laba River, Arkasara Ridge, 1500 m, 25.6.1997, I. Shokhin - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Arkhыз, Abishara-Akhuba Ridge, Dzhumarykly-Tebe Mt. [43°36'7"N, 41°14'41"E], 1800 m, 11.7.2009, A. Zubov - ML; **Kabardino-Balkaria Republic.** 1 male, Dolina Narzanov, 1964 - MD; 1 female, Tyrnyauz, 1800-2200 m, 6.6.1988, M. Danilevsky - MD; **Republic of North Ossetia-Alania.** 1 female, Fiagdon, 1.8.1983 - MD; **Republic of South Ossetia - the State of Alania.** 1 male, Tskhinvali, 7.1929, Zurinov - ZMM; **Georgia:** Holotype, male with 7 labels: 1) [white] "type"; 2) [white] "Caucase"; 3) [white] "*agap. subnigra* / Pic. (Georgie) / *subnigra* p. 119"; 4) [white] "Museum Paris / Coll. M. Pic" 5) [red] "HOLOTYPE"; 6) [white] "HOLOTYPE / *Agapanthia* / *subnigra* Pic, 1890"; 7) [white] "MNHN, Paris / EC26187" - MNHN; 6 females, Abastumani, VII. - ZMM; 1 male, Abastumani, 8.7.1895 - ZMM; 2 females, Abastumani, 20-30.6.1914 - ZMM; 1 male, south slope of Svaneti Ridge, Lentrkhi district, 9 km NW Kheledy, 1800-1900 m, 8-11.7.2005 - MD; 1 male, Tehuri River, 2000 m, 30.6.1989, A. Koval - MD; 1 female, Martvili distr., left bank of Tekhuri River, 15-30.6.2005 - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Imeretia, N slope of

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Meskhetsky Ridge, 6 km S Sairme, 1000 m, 23-026.6. 2006, A. Puchkov - MD; 2 females, Imeretia, Meskhetsky Ridge, Zekari Pass, 2100-2200 m, 26-30.6.2006, A. Puchkov - MD; 2 males, Lebarde, 42°44'20"N, 42°30'04"E, 1600 m, A. Zubov - MD; 3 males, E Tbilisi, Lori River, S Sagarejo, 19.6.2015, Snižek - SM & ML; 1 male, 1 female, 50 km S Kutisi, SE Sairme, Zekari pass, 22.6.2015, Snižek - ML; 1 male, SE Tbilisi, Udabno, 30.6.2015, Snižek - SM; **Republic of Abkhazia.** 1 male, Mont. Gagra, 6000', A. Zolotarew - ZMM; 1 male, Gagra, 5.7.1932 - MD; 1 male, Gagra, 6.1936 - MD; 1 male, Mamzyshkha Mt., 11.6.1986, N. Okhrimenko - MD; 1 male, 3 females, westwards Bzyb Ridge, Anzhulyara Mt. [43°20'N, 40°28'E], 1250-1600 m, 15.6.2004, V. Savitsky - MD; 2 males, 2 females, Mt. Atchibakh, 15 km W Pskhu, 23.6.2009, A. Gusakov - MD; 2 males, congluent of Avadkhara and Lashepse, 1470 m, 43°29'49"N, 40°39'43"E, 12.7.2009, A. Bondarenko - MD; 3 females, Bzyb vall., 1000-1600 m, 23.6.2009, A. Prosvirov - ML & SM; 1 female, Bzyb vall., 600 m, 4.7.2009, A. Prosvirov - SM; 1 male, Pyv Pass, 1880 m, 43°29'22"N, 40°41'18"E, 26.6.2010, A. Bondarenko - MD.

Distribution. High mountains of Caucasus and Transcaucasia.

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Figs 5-6. *A. (E.) v. helianthi* Plavilstshikovi, 1935, **stat. n.**: 5. Lectotype, male; 6. set of labels.

Figs 7-9. *A. (E.) v. subnigra* Pic, 1890, **stat. n.**: 7. Holotype, male; 8. lateral view; 9. set of labels.

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Aganthia (Eoptes) villosoviridescens syunika ssp. n.

Figs 10-13, Map 1

Type locality. Armenia, Syunik province, Meghri, Gumorantz, 38°59'49.20"N, 46°22'35.76"E, 1516 m.

Description. Antennae protruding beyond elytral apex with 4 joints, about one third longer than body; long oblique setae concentrated at 3rd joint apex; basal parts of antennal joints with very fine pale pubescence, and look rather dark; basal parts of middle antennal joints not reddish; prothorax about as long as wide, and about as wide anteriorly, as posteriorly; pronotum with wide well-developed dense yellow stripes; elytra shining, without microsculpture, with very poor recumbent pubescence, nearly glabrous, grey humeral elytral stripe absent; with indistinct setae spots, slightly shiny, without blue luster; erect setae concentrate anteriorly, diminished posteriorly; grey humeral elytral stripe absent; body length in males: 11.2-15.7 mm, in females: 15.9-18.1 mm.

The taxon is very close to *A. (E.) v. lederi* Ganglbauer, 1884 from which it can be easily distinguished by short antennae.

Material. Armenia: Holotype, male, Syunik province, Meghri, Gumorantz, 38°59'49.20"N, 46°22'35.76"E, 1516 m, 30.5.2013, S. Murzin - ML; 22 paratypes; 1 female, Mt. Khustup, 4.7.1982, M. Danilevsky - MD; 2 males, Shikahogh, 3.7.1981, M. Kalashian - MD; 1 male, Shikahogh, 19.6.1982, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 female, Nor Arajadzor, 39.3404°N, 46.4166°E, 1360 m, 18-21.5.2014, S. Murzin, J. Hron - SM; 1 male, Svarants, 39°21'21''N, 46°12'27''E, 1880 m, 4.5.2013, A. Rubenyan - MD; 5 males, 4 females, Khndzoresk, 39.50193°N, 46.4326°E, 1260 m, 16-22.5.2014, S. Murzin - SM & ML; 1 male, Khndzoresk, 39.5026°N, 46.4316°E, 1300 m, 22-25.5.2013, S. Murzin - ML; 1 female, Khndzoresk, 39.5°N, 46.43°E, 1300 m, 10.6.2016, S. Murzin - SM; **Azerbaijan:** 1 male, 16.5 km NW Zangilan, 39°11'35.4"N 46°31'23.5"E, 967 m, 5-6.5.2013, A. Rubenyan - MD; 1 male, Nakhichevan, Bichenek, 9.6.1982, M. Danilevsky - MD; 2 males, 1 female, Nakhichevan, Ordubad, 5.5.1987, Davydyan - ML.

Figs 10-11. *A. (E.) v. syunika* **ssp. n.:** 10. Holotype, male, Syunik province, Meghri, Gumorantz, 38°59'49.20"N, 46°22'35.76"E, 1516 m, 30.5.2013, S. Murzin; 11. Paratype, male, Armenia, Syunik province, Svarants, 1880 m, 39°21'21''N, 46°12'27''E, 4.5.2013, A. Rubenyan.

Figs 12-13. *A. (E.) v. syunika* **ssp. n.:** 12. Paratype, male, 16.5 km NW Zangilan, 39°11'35.4"N 46°31'23.5"E, 967 m, 5-6.5.2013, A. Rubenyan; 13. Paratype, females, Khndzoresk, 39.50193°N, 46.4326°E, 1260 m, 16-22.5.2014, S. Murzin.

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Distribution. Armenia, Syunik province: Meghri, Gumorantz, 38°59'49.20"N, 46°22'35.76"E, 1516 m; Khustup Mt.; Shikahogh; Nor Arajadzor, 39°20'25.4451"N, 46°24'59.7684"E, 1360 m; Svarants, 39°21'21''N, 46°12'27''E, 1880 m; Khndzoresk (39°30'6.9531"N, 46°25'57.3684"E, 1260 m; 39°30'9.3651"N, 46°25'53.7684"E, 1300 m). Azerbaijan: 16.5 km NW Zangilan, 39°11'35.4"N 46°31'23.5"E, 967 m; Nakhichevan, Bichenek; Nakhichevan, Ordubad.

Etymology. The new taxon is named after the province of the type locality.

***Agapanthia (Epoptes) villosviridescens murzini* ssp. n.**

Figs 14-15, Map 1

Type locality. Armenia, Gegharkunik province, Ayagut, 40°40'30.7251"N, 45°12'15.1285"E, 1420 m.

Description. Antennae in males protruding beyond elytral apex with 5 joints, about one half longer than body, in females antennae protruding beyond elytral apex with 3 joints, about one fifth longer than body; long oblique setae strongly concentrated at 3rd joint apex, forming poor setae tuft; pronotum in males transverse, distinctly widened posteriorly; with wide well-developed dense yellow stripes; elytra with very poor recumbent pubescence, but with dense erect setae up to the apex, with indistinct setae spots, without microsculpture, slightly shiny, without blue luster; grey humeral elytral stripe absent; body length in males: 12.3-15.2 mm; in females: 15.6-17.5 mm.

The taxon is very close to *A. (E.) v. syunika* ssp. n., but antennae are distinctly longer and prothorax widened posteriorly.

Material. Armenia: Holotype, male, Armenia, Ayagut, 40.6752°N, 45.2042°E, 1420 m, 12-13.6.2016, S. Murzin - ML; 6 paratypes; 1 male with the same label - ML; 1 male, Armenia, Ayagut, 40.6752°N, 45.2042°E, 1420 m, 1-4.6.2016, S. Murzin - ML; 1 male, Armenia, Gegharkunik prov., Ayagut, 40°40'30.72"N, 45°12'14.40"E, 1432 m, 30.6.2023, S. Murzin - SM; 1 male, Armenia, Gegharkunik prov., Ayagut, 40°40'30.72"N, 45°12'14.40"E, 1432 m, 18.5-15.6.2023, S. Murzin - SM; 1 female, Armenia, Gegharkunik prov., Ayagut, 40°40'30.72"N, 45°12'14.40"E, 1432 m, 23.6.2023, S. Murzin

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- ML; 1 female, Armenia, Gegharkunik prov., Ayagut, 40°40'30.72"N, 45°12'14.40"E, 1432 m, 13.7.2023, S. Murzin - SM.

Distribution. North Armenia, Gegharkunik province, Ayagut environs.

***Agapanthia (Epoptes) villosoviridescens lederi* Ganglbauer, 1884**

Figs 16-17, Map 2

Agapanthia lineatocollis var. *lederi* Ganglbauer, 1884: 542 - "Caucasus".

Agapanthia (s. str.) *villosoviridescens*, Pic, 1910: 97, part. (= *lineatocollis* Donovan. = *angusticollis* Gyll.), part. (including v. *lederi* Ganglb., v. *subchalybaea* Reitt., v. *subacuta* Pic).

Agapanthia subchalybaea subchalybaea, Plavilstshikov, 1929b: 136, part. - "Nord-Kaukasus: Groznyj", "Kuban: Vashtrek", "Fl. Laba", "Anapa", "Central-Kaukasus: Teberda, 7000'", "Majcop", "Vladikavkas", "Lars", "Atshish'cho", "West-Kaukasus: Krasnaja Poljana", "Sotshi", "Abchasia: Gagry, 5000'", "Transkaukasien: Mz'chet", "Borzhom", "Abas-Tuman", "Teliani", "Manglis", "Bacuriani", "Suram", "Kusary", "Kars", "Talysh".

Agapanthia villosoviridescens var. *lederi*, Winkler, 1929: 1213; Villiers, 1978: 433.

Agapanthia (s. str.) *villosoviridescens* var. *lederi*, Plavilstshikov, 1930b: 32, 40, part. - "Kaukasus".

Type locality. According to Tavakilian & Chevillotte (23 November 2022), the type locality of *Agapanthia (Epoptes) lederi* Gang. is Talysh area of Caucasian Azerbaijan. So, traditional attribution of the origin of the species to the north-west Caucasus was not correct. The type specimens of *A. (E.) lederi* were collected in Talysh area by H. Leder, who often collected in Talysh, where *Clytus arietis lederi* Ganglbauer, 1882 was also described from.

Figs 14-15. *A. (E.) v. murzini* **ssp. n.:** 14. Holotype, male, Armenia, Ayagut, 40.6752°N, 45.2042°E, 1420 m, 12-13.6.2016, S. Murzin; 15. Paratype. female, Armenia, Gegharkunik prov., Ayagut, 40°40'30.72"N, 45°12'14.40"E, 1432 m, 23.6.2023, S. Murzin.

Figs 16-17. *A. (E.) v. lederi* Ganglbauer, 1884: 16. male (paratype of *A. l. hodeki* Danilevsky, 2018), Azerbaijan, Talysh, 17.7.1981, S. Nikireev; 17. female, (paratype of *A. l. hodeki* Danilevsky, 2018), Azerbaijan, Talysh, Avrora, 28.5.1979, M. Danilevsky.

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Description. Antennae in males surpassing elytral apices by 5-6 apical joints, in females - by 3-4 joints; basal parts of antennal joints with very fine pale pubescence, and look rather dark; basal parts of middle antennal joints usually reddish; 3rd antennal joint with apical setae concentration; prothorax in males about as long as wide, and about as wide anteriorly, as posteriorly; in females prothorax transverse with wide hind part; pronotum with wide and dense central setae stripe; elytra shining, but without blue luster, without microsculpture, with very poor greyish pubescence, never hiding elytral surface; grey humeral elytral stripe absent; erect elytral setae long and dense along anterior elytral third, and gradually shortened posteriorly; elytral apices slightly attenuated in males, or rounded in females; body length in available males: 10.3-16.6 mm, in available females: 16.1-16.7 mm.

The taxon is very close to *A. (E.) v. hodeki* Danilevsky, 2018 from north-west Iran because of nearly glabrous elytra and very long antennae; but *A. (E.) v. lederi* distinctly more shining, with very smooth elytral interspaces, without microsculpture, bigger elytral punctation.

Material. Azerbaijan: 7 paratypes of *A. (E.) l. hodeki* Danilevsky, 2018: 1 male, Talysh, 10.5.1988, Voronin - MD; 1 male, 2 females, Talysh, 17.7.1981, S. Nikireev - MD; 1 female, Avrora, 28.5.1979, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 female, Talysh, Avrora, 7.5.1983, S. Nikireev - MD; 1 male, “Kasp. Meer.-Geb. / Talysch / 1897 Korb” - MD; 1 male, “Talysch / 1897 Corb” - ZMM; 1 male, Talysh, Alekseevka, 9.6.1920, J. Safronov - ZMM.

Distribution. Azerbaijan, Talysh, Lerik and Avrora (Hirkan).

***Agapanthia (Epoptes) villosoviridescens hodeki* Danilevsky, 2018**
Figs 18-19, Map 2

Agapanthia lederi hodeki Danilevsky, 2018: 181, part. – “Iran, p.Gilan, Rostamabad, 12 km W, 1550 m, 36°55', 49°23'”, “Iran, NW, prov. Gilan, Salaneh Sar, 20 km W Rostamabad”; “Talysch”, “Lerik”, Talysh, Avrora”; 2020: 302, part. - Azerbaijan (Talysh), Iran.

Type locality. Northern Iran, Gilan province, Rostamabad environs (36°55'N, 49°23'E).

Figs 18-19. *A. (E.) v. hodeki* Danilevsky, 2018: 18. Holotype, male, Iran, prov. Gilan, 12 km W Rostamabad, 36°55'N, 49°23'E, 6.6.2017, K. Hodek; 19. Paratype, female with same label.

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Description. Antennae in males protruding beyond elytral apex with 5 joints, about one half longer than body, in female antennae protruding beyond elytral apex with 3 joints, about one fifth longer than body; basal parts of antennal joints with very fine pale pubescence, and look rather dark; basal parts of middle antennal joints never reddish; long oblique setae a little concentrated at 3rd joint apex; pronotum in males transverse, distinctly widened posteriorly; with wide well-developed dense yellow stripes; elytra with poor blue luster and distinct microsculpture; grey humeral elytral stripe absent; recumbent elytral pubescence, almost completely absent; short erect setae distinct up to the apex; elytral apices slightly attenuated; body length in males: 14.5-15.7 mm; in female: 16.2 mm.

The taxon is very close to *A. (E.) v. lederi* Ganglbauer, 1884 but differs by noticeable blue luster.

Material. Iran: Holotype, male, Iran, prov. Gilan, 12 km W Rostamabad, 36°55'N, 49°23'E, 6.6.2017, K. Hodek - MD; 2 paratypes: 1 male, 1 female with same label - MD. 1 male, Kaleibar env., Makidi, 1450-1650 m, 38.8406°N, 46.9102°E, 6-7.6.2013. S. Murzin - ML.

Distribution. Northern Iran, Gilan province, Rostamabad environs, 1550 m (36°55'N, 49°23'E); Northwestern Iran, East Azerbaijan province, Kaleibar environs., Makidi, 1450-1650 m (38°50'26.1651"N, 46°54'36.7284"E).

Agapanthia (Epoptes) villosoviridescens giresunica ssp. n.

Figs 20-21, Map 3

Type locality. Turkey, Giresun province, Kumbet, 40°32'41.4294"N, 38°26'2.0124"E, 1748 m.

Description. The subspecies is characterized by matte black elytra without bluish luster; antennae reaching elytral apex by 7th-8th joints in males, in females - by 9th-10th joints; basal parts of antennal joints with very fine pale pubescence, and look rather dark; basal parts of middle antennal joints never reddish; 3rd antennal joint without apical setae concentration; elytral cuticle usually with distinct microsculpture; recumbent elytral pubescence moderately developed; erect elytral setae very short, nearly indistinct; antennae in males reaching elytral apex by 8th joint,

Figs 20-21. *A. (E.) v. giresunica* ssp. n.: 20. Holotype, male, Giresun province, Kumbet, 40°32'41.4294"N, 38°26'2.0124"E, 1748 m, 16.6.2002, N. Auvray; 21. Paratype, female, S Giresun, Kumbet, 1700 m, 26.6.1995, N. Auvray.

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in females - by 10th-11th joints; body length in males: 12.7-14.8 mm, in females: 14.2-18.2 mm.

Material. Turkey: Holotype, 1 male, Giresun province, Kumbet, 40°32'41.4294"N, 38°26'2.0124"E, 1748 m, 16.6.2002, N. Auvray - ML; 18 paratypes (ML, SM & MD); 1 male, 2 females with the same label; 2 males, 3 females, S Giresun, Kumbet, 1700 m, 26.6.1995, N. Auvray; 2 males, 2 females, Kumbet, (Giresun), 1700 m, 40.54484°N, 38.43389°E, 2.7.2001, N. Auvray; 1 male, 1 female, Giresun, Kumbet, 21.6.1994, C. Auvray; 1 female, Giresun, Kumbet, 29.6.1994, C. Auvray - MD; 1 female, S Giresun, Pinarlar env., 950 m, 40.6543°N, 38.3661°E, 20.5.-10.6.2012, J. Hron, S. Murzin; 1 male, 1 female, Giresun, Kumbet, 11.7.1996 - MD.

Distribution. North-Eastern Turkey, Giresun province, Kumbet environs and Pinarlar environs.

Etymology. The new taxon is named after the province of the type locality.

***Agapanthia (Eoptes) villosoviridescens shankhizai* ssp. n.**

Figs 22-23, Map 3

Type locality. Turkey, Denizli province, eastern edge of Denizli.

Description. Antennae in males protruding beyond elytral apex with 6 joints, about one half longer than elytral length; in females antennae reaching elytral apex by 9th joint; basal parts of antennal joints with very fine pale pubescence, slightly reddish; erect apical setae of 3rd antennal joint distinctly condensed apically; prothorax with wide yellow central stripe; in male about 1.1 times wider at bases than long, in females - about 1.2 times; elytra with poorly developed pubescence and short dense erect setae; setae patches of recumbent pubescence hardly pronounced; elytral microsculpture poorly developed; body length in male: 17.2 mm; in females: 17.4-18.5 mm.

Material. Holotype, 1 male, Turkey, Denizli province, eastern edge of Denizli, 20.5.2015, E. Shankhiza - ML. 2 paratypes; 2 females, with the same label - MD & ML.

Distribution. South-Western Turkey, Denizli province.

Etymology. The new taxon is dedicated to E.V. Shankhiza, who collected the type series.

Figs 22-23. *A. (E.) v. shankhizai* **ssp. n.:** 22. Holotype, male, Turkey, Denizli province, eastern edge of Denizli, 20.5.2015, E. Shankhiza; 23. paratype, female with same label.

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***Agapanthia (Epopetes) villosoviridescens gazanchidisi* Lazarev,
2021, stat. n.**

Figs 24-25, Map 4

Agapanthia (Epopetes) gazanchidisi Lazarev, 2021: 31 - "Eastern Greece, Dasochori env. 40°53'48.67"N, 24°48'26.12"E".

Type locality. Eastern Greece, Dasochori environs, 40°53'48.67"N, 24°48'26.12"E.

Description. Body moderately elongated; antennae very thin, black, with disperse setae tufts, in males reaching beyond elytral apices by 5 joints, in females - by 3 joints; 3rd antennal joint slightly lightened basally in Bulgarian specimens; 1st and 2nd joints covered with black pubescence; about three basal fourth of 3rd joint covered with pale fine recumbent pubescence, apical fourth with black pubescence; whole length of 3rd joint with long suberect setae concentrated apically; others joints covered with white pubescence to about half; 3rd antennal joint is the longest, 4th and 5th joints both shorter than 1st; prothorax about as long as its basal width, slightly convex laterally; pronotum with dense central and lateral, moderately wide yellow lines, less pronounced in Greek specimens; pronotal punctation regular, very dense, but not conjugated; elytra in males about 3.1 times longer than wide, in females - 3.0 times, parallel sided; with distinct microsculpture with nearly indistinct, small transverse yellow patches (better developed in Bulgarian specimens) and glabrous in between; with numerous erect black setae diminished apically and sometimes totally disappearing in posterior elytral half; elytral apices rounded; elytral punctation very dense, partly transversally conjugated; body length in males: 10.8-15.8 mm, body length in females: 12.4-17.7 mm.

Material. Greece: Holotype, 1 male, Eastern Greece, Dasochori env. 40°53'48.67"N, 24°48'26.12"E, 5.7.2021, V. Gazanchidis leg. - ML; 21 paratypes; 2 males (VG), 1 female (ML) with same label; 1 female, Macedonia, Katerini dist., Paralia, 6.6.1997, J. Macek leg. - SM; **Bulgaria:** 1 female, Tchernvenata Stena reserve, 41°54'36"N, 24°52'33"E, 1213 m, 29.6.2014, T. Ljubomirov leg. - MD; 1 female, W Popkralevo vill., 43°59'38"N, 27°20'34"E, 50 m, 13.5.2012, T. Ljubomirov leg. - MD; 1 male, 1 female, N Sudievo, 42°40'35"N,

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27°19'27"E, 137 m, 21.5.2012, T. Ljubomirov leg. - MD; 3 males, 4 females, Lozenska Planina Mts., SE German vill., 780 m, 17.6.2004, T. Ljubomirov leg. - MD; 1 female, E Stroumeshnitsa vill., 41°23'N, 23°03'E, 170 m, 16.6.2009, T. Ljubomirov leg. - MD; 1 male, SW Gabrovo vill., 41°52'10"N, 22°56'31"E, 1029 m, 8.6.2012, T. Ljubomirov leg. - MD; 1 female, E Kayazhevo, 42°06'39"N, 26°31'14"E, 99 m, 24.6.2012, T. Ljubomirov leg. - MD; 1 female, Etropolevska Planina Mts., Ravna River riverside, 42°49'N, 23°49'E, 610 m, 6.6.2006, T. Ljubomirov leg. - MD; 1 female, NW Vassil Levsky vill., 43°57'39"N, 27°21'47"E, 125 m, 13.5.2012, T. Ljubomirov leg.; 1 female, Kozhuch, 17.5.1983, J. Ganev leg. - MD.

Distribution. The taxon is distributed in eastern Greece and in Bulgaria.

Agapanthia (Epoetes) villosviridescens markusi Rapuzzi, Sama & Kotán, 2013, stat. n.

Figs 26-27, Map 4

Agapanthia (Epoetes) markusi Rapuzzi, Sama & Kotán, 2013: 583 - "Greece, Ipiros, Ioanina pref., 7 Km SW Metsovo, 1360 m", Greece: Ipiros, Varnous Mts., Trikala, Ioannina, Florina, Kastoria, Pindos, Macedonia; Steiner & Schmid, 2013: 2 "Griechenland"; Danilevsky, 2020: 303 - Albania, Greece.

Agapanthia markusi, Kovács, 2015: 53 - "Albania, Korçë district, Opari area, Moglicë, E of the village, 40°42'25.2", 20°25'04.6" 525 m".

Type locality. Greece, Epirus, Ioannina, 7 km SW Metsovo, 1360 m.

Description. Antennae relatively short, about one third longer than elytra, reaching elytral apex by 8th joints in males, in females - by 10th joints; basal parts of antennal joints with very fine pale pubescence, and look rather dark; basal parts of middle antennal joints often reddish; 3rd antennal joint with apical setae concentration; prothorax in males about as long as wide, and slightly widened posteriorly; in females prothorax transverse with wider hind part; pronotum glabrous, without central setae stripe; elytra with indistinct recumbent pubescence, but with dense erect setae present up to the apex; elytral punctation very dense, nearly conjugated; microsculpture sometimes distinct; body length in males: 10.4-14.5 mm; in females: 12.8-15.1 mm.

A. (E.) v. markusi Rapuzzi, Sama & Kotán, 2013 is very

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close to *A. (E.) v. gazanchidisi* Lazarev, 2021, but differs by several small characters: *A. (E.) v. gazanchidisi* is distinctly narrower, pronotal setae stripe better developed, humeral angles more obliterated, elytral punctation finer.

Material. Greece: 2 males, 3 females, Pindos, Metsova, Katara Pass, 1700 m, 5.7.2008 - MD; 1 male, Kastoria, 31.5.2008 - MD.

Distribution. According to the original description, known localities are: Greece: Ipiros, Joannina pref., 7 km SW Metsovo, 1360 m; Varnous Mts., 1450 m, Agios Germanos; Trikala, Katara pass; Ioannina, Metsovo e Grevena; Trikala, Katara pass, 1400-1700 m; Florina, Pisoderion, Agios Triados, 1400 m; Ioannina, Katara pass, 1650 m, 39°47'48''N 21°13'49''E; Kastoria, Mt. Vernon, 1900 m; Pindos, Peristeri, 1400 m; Ipiros, Aoos lake; Ipiros, Milia; Macedonia, pref. Imathia, Mt. Vermio, 6 km W Naousa, 1041 m; Ipiros, pref. Joannina, 2 km W Fourka, 1450 m. Albania: Korçë district, Opari area, Moglicë, E of the village, 40°42'25.2'', 20°25'04.6'', 525 m.

Figs 24-25. *A. (E.) v. gazanchidisi* Lazarev, 2021, **stat. n.**:
24. Holotype, male, Eastern Greece, Dasochori env. 40°53'48.67"N,
24°48'26.12"E, 5.7.2021, V. Gazanchidis leg.; 25. paratype, female
with same label.

Figs 26-27. A. (*E.*) *v. markusi* Rapuzzi, Sama & Kotán, 2013, **stat. n.:**
26. males, Greece, Pindos, Metsova, Katara Pass, 1700 m, 5.7.2008;
27. female with same label.

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**Key to *Agapanthia (Epoptes) villosoviridescens* (DeGeer, 1775)
subspecies**

- 1(2) Elytra usually with relatively dense pubescence, often totally hiding cuticula; body length: 10.2-21.5 mm.....
.....*A. v. villosoviridescens* (DeGeer, 1775)
- 2(1) Elytra with scattered pubescence, shining cuticula fragments always distinct.
- 3(4) Elytral pubescence hardly visible, often indistinct; bluish luster usually more or less pronounced; body length: 11.2-18.7 mm...
.....*A. v. subnigra* Pic, 1890, **stat. n.**
- 4(3) Elytral pubescence always distinct.
- 5(11) Erect elytral pubescence very short.
- 6(10) Antennae with reddish basal parts of middle joints (only one female known).
- 8(9) Prothorax nearly cylindrical (in male and in females), about as wide anteriorly as posteriorly, about 1.1-1.2 times wider basally than long; body length: 17.2-18.5 mm.....
.....*A. v. shankhizai* **ssp. n.**
- 9(8) Prothorax in females strongly widened posteriorly; humeral elytral grey stripe often distinct; body length: 10.5-21.5 mm.....
.....*A. v. helianthi* Plavilstshikov, 1935, **stat. n.**
- 10(6) Antennae never with reddish basal parts of middle joints; body length: 12.7-18.2 mm.....
.....*A. v. giresunica* **ssp. n.**
- 11(5) Erect elytral pubescence well developed back to the apex.
- 12(15) Antennae relatively short, about one third longer than body in males.
- 13(14) Antennae never with reddish basal parts of middle joints; body length: 11.2-18.1 mm.....
.....*A. v. syunika* **ssp. n.**
- 14(13) Antennae usually with reddish basal parts of middle joints; body length: 10.4-15.1 mm.....
.....*A. v. markusi* Rapuzzi, Sama & Kotán, 2013, **stat. n.**
- 15(12) Antennae relatively long, about half longer than body in males.
- 16(19) Elytra with distinct microsculpture.
- 17(18) 3rd antennal joints with disperse setae tufts; elytra without bluish luster; body length: 10.8-17.7 mm.....

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-*A. v. gazanchidisi* Lazarev, 2021, **stat. n.**
18(17) 3rd antennal joints with distinct setae tufts; elytra with poor
bluish luster; body length: 14.5-16.2 mm.....
.....*A. v. hodeki* Danilevsky, 2018
19(16) Elytra without microsculpture.
20(21) 3rd antennal joints with dense, elongated setae tufts; body
length: 12.3-17.5 mm.....
.....*A. v. murzini* **ssp. n.**
21(20) 3rd antennal joints with dispers, shortened setae tufts; body
length: 10.3-16.7 mm.....
.....*A. v. lederi* Ganglbauer, 1884

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Map 1.

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A. (*E.*) v. *helianthi* Plavilstshikovi, 1935, stat. n.: Russia: Krasnodar Region: 1-11; Republic of Adygea: 12-13; Karachay-Cherkess Republic: 14-15; Stavropol Region: 16-19; Republic of North Ossetia-Alania: 20-21; Republic of Ingushetia: 22; Chechen Republic: 23-25; Republic of Dagestan: 26-28; Georgia: 29-37; Armenia: 38-46; Azerbaijan: 47-52.

A. (*E.*) v. *subnigra* Pic, 1890, stat. n.: Russia: Krasnodar Region: 53-56; Republic of Adygea: 57-59; Karachay-Cherkess Republic: 60-63; Kabardino-Balkarian Republic: 64-65; Republic of North Ossetia-Alania: 66; Republic of South Ossetia - the State of Alania: 67; Georgia: 68-75; Republic of Abkhazia: 76-81.

A. (*E.*) v. *syunika* ssp. n.: Armenia: 82-87; Azerbaijan: 88-90.

A. (*E.*) v. *murzini* ssp. n.: Armenia: 91.

1 - Anapa; 2 - Mingrelskoe; 3 - Ekaterinodar [Krasnodar]; 4 - Ladozhskaya; 5 - Armavir; 6 - Rodnikovskaya; 7 - Bolshaya Laba River; 8 - Goryachy Klyuch, Shchetka Mt.; 9 - Betta, 44°13'45.4853"N, 39°14'24.7287"E; 10 - Sochi, Utch-Dere; 11 - Sochi; 12 - Khomuty; 13 - Maikop; 14 - Zelenchukskaya; 15 - Teberda; 16 - Kislovodsk; 17 - Zheleznovodsk; 18 - Mineralnye Vody, Mashuk; 19 - Temnolesskaya; 20 - Vladikavkaz; 21 - Mozdok; 22 - Alkun; 23 - Grozny; 24 - Naurskaya; 25 - Starogladkovskaya, Terek River; 26 - Kizlyar; 27 - Novy Biryuzak; 28 - Khasavyurt; 29 - Teliani near, Telavi; 30 - Mtskheta; 31 - Manglisi; 32 - Surami; 33 - Akhaldaba; 34 - Borjomi; 35 - Tsagveri; 36 - Bakuriani; 37 - Orbeti, Trialiti Ridge; 38 - Ditavan, 40°57'18.0051"N, 45°13'19.2086"E; 39 - Ijevan; 40 - Darachichag [Tsaghkadzor]; 41 - Arailer; 42 - Alagez [Aragats Mt.]; 43 - Inaklyu [Antarut]; 44 - Byurakan; 45 - Geghard, 40°8'29.0451"N, 44°48'26.6485"E; 46 - Khosrov, 40°02'N, 45°02'E; 47 - Akstafa; 48 - Barda; 49 - Sabir-Abad; 50 - Nukha [Shaki]; 51 - Qusar; 52 - Altyagach; 53 - Novorossiysk, Andreevsky pass, 44°43'N, 37°51'E, 500 m; 54 - Atchishkho, 1600 m; 55 - Krasnaya Polyana; 56 - Kardyvach; 57 - Abago Mt., 2100 m; 58 - Lagonaki, Ridge, Kamennoe More, 44°10'33"N, 40°03'19"E, 1760-1800 m;

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59 - westwards Tkhach Mt., 1700-1900 m; 60 - Damkhurts;
61 - Bolshaya Laba River, Pkhiya, 1400-1600 m; 62 - Bolshaya Laba
River, Arkasara Ridge, 1500 m; 63 - Arkhyz, Abishara-Akhuba
Ridge, Dzhumarykly-Tebe Mt. [43°36'7"N, 41°14'41"E], 1800 m;
64 - Dolina Narzanov; 65 - Tyrnyauz, 1800-2200 m; 66 - Fiagdon;
67 - Tskhinvali; 68 - Tehuri River, 2000 m; 69 - Lebarde,
42°44'20"N, 42°30'04"E, 1600 m; 70 - south slope of Svaneti Ridge,
Lentrkhi district, 9 km NW Kheledy, 1800-1900 m; 71 - N slope of
Meskhetsky Ridge, 6 km S Sairme, 1000 m; 72 - Meskhetsky Ridge,
Zekari Pass, 2100-2200 m; 73 - Abastumani; 74 - Lori River,
S Sagarejo; 75 - Udabno; 76 - Pyv Pass, 43°29'22"N, 40°41'18"E,
1880 m; 77 - congluent of Avadkhara and Lashepse, 43°29'49"N,
40°39'43"E, 1470 m; 78 - Atchibakh Mt., 15 km W Pskhu;
79 - Gagra; 80 - Mamzyshkha Mt.; 81 - westwards Bzyb Ridge,
Anzhulyara Mt. [43°20'N, 40°28'E], 1250-1600 m; 82 - Gumorantz,
38°59'49.20"N, 46°22'35.76"E, 1516 m; 83 - Shikahogh;
84 - Khustup Mt.; 85 - Nor Arajadzor, 39°20'25.4451"N,
46°24'59.7684"E, 1360 m; 86 - Svarants, 39°21'21''N, 46°12'27''E,
1880 m; 87 - Khndzoresk, 39°30'9.3651"N, 46°25'53.7684"E,
1300 m; 88 - 16.5 km NW Zangilan, 39°11'35.4"N 46°31'23.5"E,
967 m; 89 - Nakhichevan, Bichenek; 90 - Nakhichevan, Ordubad;
91 - Armenia, Ayagut, 40°40'30.7251"N, 45°12'15.1285"E, 1420 m.

Map 2.

A. (E.) v. *lederi* Ganglbauer, 1884: Azerbaijan: 1 - Lerik; 2 - Avrora [Hirkan].

A. (E.) v. *hodeki* Danilevsky, 2018: Iran: 3 - Gilan, 12 km W Rostamabad, 36°55'N, 49°23'E; 4 - Makidi, 38°50'26.1651"N, 46°54'36.7284"E, 1450-1650 m.

Map 3.

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A. (*E.*) v. *giresunica* ssp. n.: Turkey, Giresun province: 1 - Kumbet, 40°32'41.4294"N, 38°26'2.0124"E, 1748 m; 2 - Pinarlar environs, 40°39'15.4854"N, 38°21'57.9684"E, 950 m.

A. (*E.*) v. *shankhizai* ssp. n.: 3 - Turkey, Denizli province, eastern edge of Denizli.

Map 4.

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A. (E.) v. *markusi* Rapuzzi, Sama & Kotán, 2013, stat. n.: Greece: 1-8; Albania: 9.

A. (E.) v. *gazanchidisi* Lazarev, 2021, stat. n.: Greece: 10-11; Bulgaria: 12-21.

1 - Ipiros, Ioannina pref., 7 km SW Metsovo, 1360 m; 2 - Ipiros, Aaos lake; 3 - Ioannina, Katara pass, 1650 m, 39°47'48''N 21°13'49''E; 4 - Ipiros, pref. Ioannina, 2 km W Fourka, 1450 m; 5 - Macedonia, pref. Imathia, Mt. Vermio, 6 km W Naousa, 1041 m; 6 - Florina, Pisoderion, Agios Triados, 1400 m; 7 - Varnous Mts., 1450 m, Agios Germanos; 8 -Macedonia, pref. Imathia, Mt. Vermio, 6 km W Naousa, 1041 m; 9 - Korçë district, Opari area, Moglicë, E of the village, 40°42'25.2", 20°25'04.6", 525 m; 10 - Dasochori environs, 40°53'48.67"N, 24°48'26.12"E; 11 - Macedonia, Katerini dist., Paralia; 12 - Tchervenata Stena reserve, 41°54'36"N, 24°52'33"E, 1213 m; 13 - E Kayazhevo, 42°06'39"N, 26°31'14"E, 99 m; 14 - N Sudievo, 42°40'35"N, 27°19'27"E, 137 m; 15 - NW Vassil Levsky vill., 43°57'39"N, 27°21'47"E, 125 m; 16 - W Popkralevo vill., 43°59'38"N, 27°20'34"E, 50 m; 17 - Etropolska Planina Mts., Ravna River riverside, 42°49'N, 23°49'E, 610 m; 18 - Lozenska Planina Mts., SE German vill., 780 m; 19 - SW Gabrovo vill., 41°52'10"N, 22°56'31"E, 1029 m; 20 - Kozhuch; 21 - E Stroumeshnitsa vill., 41°23'N, 23°03'E, 170 m.

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